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SoildiverAgro

Soil biodiversity enhancement in European agroecosystems to promote their stability and resilience by external inputs reduction and crop performance increase

D3.4 - REPORT ON THE RELATIONSHIPS BETWEEN SOIL BIODIVERSITY AND SOIL CHARACTERISTICS, CLIMATE CONDITIONS AND AGRICULTURAL MANAGEMENT SYSTEMS (CONVENTIONAL AND ORGANIC)

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D3.4. REPORT ON THE RELATIONSHIP BETWEEN SOIL BIODIVERSITY AND SOIL CHARACTERISTICS, CLIMATE CONDITIONS AND AGRICULTURAL MANAGEMENT SYSTEMS (CONVENTIONAL AND ORGANIC)

Summary

The soil microbiome plays key roles in terrestrial ecosystems. Importantly, it contributes significantly to ecosystem services such as food production, climate regulation, pest control, and maintenance of soil, water and air quality. Results of the analysis of the soil samples taken to gain more knowledge about the current status of the biological, genetic and/or functional diversity of soil organisms in wheat producing croplands across different European pedoclimatic regions exhibited significant positive or negative relationships with a variety of environmental parameters resulting respectively in a higher and lower prokaryotic and/or fungal diversity. Further analysis revealed that certain physiochemical parameters are useful as microbiological drivers in some pedoclimatic regions. However, significant correlations also could be identified with the most abundant prokaryotic genera or abundance of the investigated functional genes, or with a particular widespread fungal taxon, seemingly a potential candidate as indicator group, suggesting that these environmental parameters may play a crucial role in shaping the microbiome and its functionality across all nine pedoclimatic regions. Additionally, specific farming practices were found to exert profound impacts on certain prokaryotic genera as variations in their abundance could be noticed.

Next to the prokaryotic and fungal taxonomic composition, the total microbial abundance was investigated as well. The biomass, or abundance, can be interpreted as a measurement of the microbial "reservoir" in soils. Hence, the maintenance and/or increase of this parameter in soils is of significant importance for agricultural sustainability. Although significant positive or negative correlations between microbial biomass and a variety of environmental parameters could be recorded, no significant effects of the farming system was found. These results are in agreement with the aforementioned results, including these concerning the farming system as specific farming practices impact certain microbes differently with the possibility to counteract each other.

Also nematodes play diverse and important roles in soil ecosystems and were included into the investigation. Again, results showed significant positive or negative relationships with a variety of environmental parameters, including most of the climatic parameters. Some of these environmental parameters also affected Prokaryotes, fungi or both organism group biodiversity. In 2 regions none of the farming management practices influenced the nematode communities significantly. In the other regions, the use of phytoproducts, different soil fertility management methods, tillage practices and/or the crop rotation system caused considerable shifts in nematode communities, in some cases even the functional diversity. Results cautiously suggest that application of mineral fertilizers and phytoproducts causes a less healthy soil condition compared to organic or no application of fertilizer and no usage of phytoproducts. The effect of different tillage methods is less clear.

Earthworms are key members of soil fauna communities with functional roles as physical and chemical engineers by modifying soil structure and regulating nutrient cycles and as biological regulators shaping soil biota communities. Therefore, they were also collected and analysed. Temperature was the climatic factor with the strongest impact on earthworm diversity. Of the soil properties, a negative association of soil pH and bioavailable Fe with the proportion of anecic earthworms was also detected. None of the variables describing the agricultural management had statistically discernible effects on earthworm density, biomass or species richness.

The relationship between the obtained OTUs and ASVs from prokaryotes, fungi and nematodes was described using co-abundance networks. Clusters of highly related OTUs were identified and related to meta-information on soil characteristics, climatological and agricultural data. Results still showed a large number of complex interactions, making it impossible to identify the key associations between metadata variables and biodiversity. Hence, a relevance association network was performed for each area to identify the key associations for each pedoclimatic area. Variables related to the pH, different form of total C, those related to the nitrogen content, CaCO₃, SO₄, Mn, Zn and NO₃ are identified as relevant for certain regions. Also environmental variables (temperature or precipitation) and some soil physical properties (silt, sand or the aggregates size distribution) are sparingly identified as key. Finally, certain management practices also are identified as a key variable in several regions.

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Introduction

Historically the path of global agricultural development has been narrowly focused on increased productivity rather than on resource management. At present, research is scaled up in Europe to implement sustainable primary production systems. This is necessary to reduce the burden of agriculture on natural ecosystems but also to avoid the depletion of the natural resources on which agricultural production depends. Quality improvement and sustainable management of soils require soil health monitoring, including biological indicators, to relate land use and soil management to soil biota diversity and soil functioning. However, compared with successful restoration events of above-ground ecosystems, our knowledge of soil health improvement is still very poor. This is partly because soil formation is considered to be a very slow process when it happens under natural conditions (Harrison et al., 2008), in contrast, agricultural practices can influence soil properties and fertility more rapidly (Knops et al., 2000).

Workpackage 3 of the SoildiverAgro-project aims at expanding knowledge about the current status of the biological, genetic and/or functional diversity of soil organisms in wheat producing croplands across different European pedoclimatic regions and relate it to different production systems (conventional and organic farming). The results of this study can be found in Deliverable Report D3.3. However, although the measured biodiversity is affected by the production systems as a whole, separate treatments and other factors potentially play a more important role compared to others. This deliverable report (D3.4) goes into this more in detail to eventually reveal which of the physical, chemical, climatological and agricultural factors influence the biodiversity of the different organism groups the most.

During a survey throughout 9 pedoclimatic regions (Atlantic Central (Atl_cent), Atlantic North (Atl_north), Boreal, Continental (Cont), Lusitanian (Lusit), Mediterranean North (Med_north), Mediterranean South (Med_south), Nemoral, Pannonian (Pann)), a total of 188 wheat fields of conventional and organic farming systems were sampled. From each sample, the diversity of the following organism groups was investigated: bacteria, fungi, nematodes and earthworms. As mentioned before, deliverable report D3.3 describes about the results of the biological, functional and/or genetic biodiversity of the investigated organism groups solely in relation to the agricultural management systems (conventional vs. organic) and the 9 pedoclimatic regions. This deliverable report (D3.4) can be regarded as an extension of deliverable report D3.3 because it investigates the relationship of each organism group with indepth data not yet used for D3.3.

The data used to interrelate with the biodiversity results concerns the different treatments within each agricultural system, the chemical and physical soil characteristics, and the climatological conditions. All the data, with exception of the chemical and physical soil characteristics (see deliverable D3.2) was collected in different tables which can be found at the end of this report (annexes-tables):

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- Metadatafile 1 – geographical data
- Metadatafile 2 – climatological data
- Metadatafile 3 – management practices

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1 Prokaryotic diversity

1.1 Introduction

The soil microbiome plays key roles for the functioning of terrestrial ecosystems, influencing soil structure formation, organic matter decomposition, nutrient cycling, energy flow, and biodegradation of pollutants (Van Der Heijden *et al.*, 2008; Nazir *et al.*, 2010; Nielsen *et al.*, 2011; Delgado-Baquerizo, Reich, *et al.*, 2020). Additionally, soil microbes contribute significantly to ecosystem services such as food production, climate regulation, pest control, and maintenance of water and air quality (Barrios, 2007; Bender *et al.*, 2016).

Within the realm of soil microorganisms, prokaryotes stand out as the most abundant and diverse group, actively participating in various ecosystem functions and services (Treseder *et al.*, 2012; Regan *et al.*, 2014). Particularly in agroecosystems, soil prokaryotes play a pivotal role in crop productivity, soil health, and agricultural sustainability (Van Der Heijden *et al.*, 2008). Their beneficial interactions with plants include enhancing nutrient uptake, suppressing soil-borne diseases, improving soil water retention, and promoting plant growth (Garbeva *et al.*, 2004; Bhattacharyya *et al.*, 2020). Thus, maintaining high prokaryotic diversity is crucial for ensuring quality crop production, reducing disease impact, and serving as an indicator of soil health (Abawi and Widmer, 2000; Schloter *et al.*, 2003).

Factors such as climate, soil properties, and vegetation have been identified as significant influencers of the soil microbiome (Jansson and Hofmockel, 2020; Wang *et al.*, 2020; Labouyrie *et al.*, 2023). For instance, climate variables like warming and humidity serve as predictors of soil-borne pathogens and fungal disease outbreaks worldwide (Delgado-Baquerizo, Guerra, *et al.*, 2020; Romero *et al.*, 2022). Among soil properties, pH emerges as a key driver in shaping microbial communities, followed by soil organic matter content, texture, and nutrient availability (Fierer and Jackson, 2006; Lauber *et al.*, 2008; Liu *et al.*, 2023).

Agricultural management practices significantly impact soil physicochemical properties and microbial diversity (Zhou and Fong, 2021; Fox *et al.*, 2022). Intensive agricultural practices can lead to long-term detrimental effects on soil productivity, health, and microbial diversity, with adverse consequences for agriculture, the environment, and public health worldwide (Kennedy and Smith, 1995; Tilman *et al.*, 2002). Conversely, organic farming practices are associated with positive effects on soil properties and microbial abundance and diversity compared to conventional high-input farming (Gomiero *et al.*, 2011). Additionally, conservation agriculture practices, such as diversified cropping rotations, reduced tillage, and incorporation of crop residues, have shown promising results in enhancing soil biodiversity, preventing soil degradation, and promoting soil carbon sequestration and storage (Babin *et al.*, 2019; Zhang *et al.*, 2019; Kim *et al.*, 2020; Neupane *et al.*, 2021).

Despite advancements in understanding microbial shifts in farming systems and the spatial distribution of soil microbial communities, evidence regarding the impact of agricultural management systems, specific farming practices, and key environmental drivers on belowground

prokaryotic biodiversity across large spatial scales remains limited (Hartmann *et al.*, 2015; Lupatini *et al.*, 2017). Furthermore, studies focusing on wheat fields, which represent vast arable lands with high agronomic value, across a continental scale are scarce.

This study aims to address these knowledge gaps by surveying 188 wheat fields across nine European pedoclimatic zones with contrasting climatic conditions, soil properties, and two management systems (conventional and organic) with different farming practices. The objectives include evaluating differences in the prokaryotic soil microbiome across European pedoclimatic regions, assessing large-scale effects of soil properties, climate, management systems, and farming practices on the prokaryotic microbiome. We hypothesize that contrasting climatic conditions, soil properties, and management practices will lead to variations in prokaryotic communities.

1.2 Material and Methods

1.2.1 Sampling

Soil sampling was carried out in all nine pedoclimatic regions following the guidelines outlined in the Handbook of WP3 (Waeyenberge, 2020) as previously detailed in D3.3. In summary, composite samples for DNA-based identification were collected from two to three field sites within the same farm, encompassing both organic and conventional farming systems, across five different regional locations.

Subsamples targeting bacteria, fungi, and nematodes were preserved in a freezer at -80°C before being sent for DNA extraction and sequencing. Additionally, another set of samples intended for physical and chemical analyses were either sieved and stored at room temperature or dried before shipment from Spain.

1.2.2 DNA extractions, qPCR and sequencing

The DNA extraction, amplicon sequencing and qPCR of functional genes was conducted according to protocol described in the Handbook (Lassen and Brandt, 2020) and described in the previously published D3.3 report.

1.2.3 Bioinformatics

Bioinformatics for the bacterial 16s rRNA gene sequence data was conducted using the QIIME pipeline (Bolyen *et al.*, 2019) as described in the previously published D3.3 report.

1.2.4 Statistics

All analyses were conducted in R version 4.3.3 (R Core Team 2018) and R studio version 12.1.402. All figures were constructed using “microeco” (Liu *et al.*, 2021), ‘phyloseq’ (McMurdie and Holmes, 2013), “vegan” and ‘ggplot2’ (Wickham, 2016) R packages.

Connections between alpha diversity metrics and environmental parameters were investigated using Spearman’s rank correlations (Spearman, 1987). Beta-diversity was investigated with non-metric multidimensional scaling (NMDS) from the relative abundance of OTUs (proportions from the total read amounts in the sample library). NMDS was conducted with stable solution from random starts, axis scaling and species scores with function metaMDS in ‘vegan’ package 2.5-5 (vegan: Community Ecology Package, 2012) by using Bray-Curtis dissimilarity index. Environmental factors and soil physiochemical parameters (data available in Annexes-tables) were used in the NMDS to investigate their effects on the variation in prokaryotic OTU composition using the *envfit* function of the vegan package. Only the environmental factors or soil physiochemical parameters deemed to be most significantly ($p < 0.001$) associated with the prokaryotic community composition were included in the NMDS plot. Correlations between abundances of taxa, functional genes and soil physiochemical and environmental properties were investigated using Spearman’s rank test. Differential abundance analysis was used to identify genera significantly associated with specific agricultural management system (organic vs. conventional farming), or different farming practices (e.g. crop rotation system, type of fertilizers used, type of pesticides used, etc.) by using default settings of the *ancombc* function of the “ancombc” R package (Lin and Peddada, 2020). Data on agricultural management system and farming practices are available in annexes-tables.

1.3 Results

1.3.1 Interrelationship between environmental factors, physiochemical parameters and prokaryotic alpha diversity

Alpha diversity measures exhibited significant associations with a variety of environmental parameters (see Figure 1.1). For example, mean annual temperature (Temp), soil pH (pH_w, pH_KCl, pH_CaCl₂), and CaCO₃ content demonstrated a negative relationship with most alpha diversity measures, indicating a potential tendency towards lower prokaryotic diversity under these conditions. This decreased diversity also corresponded to a positive correlation with Good’s coverage index, suggesting that soil samples characterized by these parameters may require a lower sequencing depth to capture the full diversity of the respective microbiome, with a lower probability of unmeasured sequences in the sample. In contrast, parameters such as actual field moisture content (FMa), organic matter content (OM), total organic C (TOC), particulate organic C (POC), and mean annual precipitation (Precip) tended to be positively correlated with alpha diversity measures

(negatively with Coverage), implying that higher levels of these parameters may contribute to greater alpha diversity in the soil.

Figure 1.1. Spearman's rank correlations between environmental factors and various prokaryotic alpha diversity metrics. Alpha diversity metric include: Shannon, Pielou, Simpson, Inverted Simpson, Observed number of ASV (Observed), Fisher, Chao1, Abundance-based coverage estimator (ACE) and Good's coverage index (Coverage). The strength of the correlations is indicated by color intensity and asterisk indicate significance level of the correlation * $p < 0.05$, ** $p < 0.01$, *** $p < 0.001$. Abbreviations: Mean annual temperature = Temp, Mean annual precipitation = Precip, Coarse sand = CSa, Fine sand = FSa, Coarse silt = CSi, Fine silt = FSi, Sand content = SA, Silt content = SI, Clay content = CL, pH in water = pH_w, pH in KCl = pH_KCl, pH in CaCl₂ = pH_CaCl₂, Electrical conductivity = EC, Organic Matter = OM, Total organic C = TOC, Particulate organic C = POC, Total N = Nt, Cation exchange capacity = CEC, Exchangeable Ca = Caex, Exchangeable Mg = Mgex, Exchangeable K = Kex, Exchangeable Na = Naex, Sum of bases = Bs, CaCO₃ = CaCO₃, Rock fragments and gravels = Rfg, Actual field moisture content = FMa, NH₄⁺ = NH₄, NO₃⁻ = NO₃, NO₂⁻ = NO₂, P available = Pav, Cu bioavailable = Cuba, Zn bioavailable = Znba, Fe bioavailable = Feba, Mn bioavailable = Mnba, Aggregates size distribution >2000 = Agsd_b, Aggregates size distribution 250-2000 = Agsd_c, Aggregates size distribution 53-250 = Agsd_d, Aggregates size distribution <53 = Agsd_e, Aggregates mean weight diameter = AMWD.

1.3.2 Interrelationship between environmental factors, physiochemical parameters and prokaryotic beta diversity

Figure 1.2. Nonmetric multidimensional scaling (NMDS) of the amplicon sequence variants (ASVs) composition of the different pedoclimatic regions based on Bray-Curtis dissimilarities. Vectors represent environmental variables that were significantly associated with the observed variations in prokaryotic community compositions ($p < 0.001$). The length of the arrows represents the strength of the correlation between the prokaryotic community composition and environmental properties. Abbreviations: Mean annual temperature = Temp, Mean annual precipitation = Precip, Clay content = CL, pH in water = pH_w, Electrical conductivity = EC, Organic Matter = OM, Total organic C = TOC, Particulate organic C = POC, Total N = Nt, Exchangeable Ca = Caex, Exchangeable Mg = Mgex, Exchangeable Na = Naex, Sum of bases = Bs, CaCO_3 = CaCO_3 , Actual field moisture content = FMa, NH_4^+ = NH_4 , NO_3^- = NO_3 , NO_2^- = NO_2 , P available = Pav, Zn bioavailable = Znba, Fe bioavailable = Feba, Aggregates size distribution 250-2000 = Agsd_c, Aggregates size distribution 53-250 = Agsd_d. The specific regions are indicated by color; Atl_cent = Atlantic Central, Atl_north = Atlantic North, Boreal = Boreal, Cont= Continental, Lusit= Lusitanian, Med_north = Mediterranean North, Med_south = Mediterranean South, Nemoral = Nemoral, Pann = Pannonian. Agricultural management system is indicated by shape with circles being conventional (Conv) and triangles being organic (Org) farming.

The composition of the prokaryotic microbiome was distinctly influenced by pedoclimatic regions, as outlined in the D3.3 report. Through NMDS analyses, it was evident that mean annual temperature (Temp), mean annual precipitation (Precip), water extractable pH (pH_w), CaCO₃ content, sum of bases (Bs), bioavailable Fe (Feba), aggregates size distribution (Agsd_C), and actual field moisture content (FMA) had a notable impact ($r^2 > 0.3$) on the prokaryotic community composition (Figure 1.2.). Specifically, high soil pH, CaCO₃ content, and Bs were characteristic of Mediterranean regions, while NH₄ and clay (CL) content were associated with the Pannonian region. On the other hand, precipitation, particulate organic C (POC), organic matter content (OM), and total organic C (TOC) were indicative of the Lusitanian region.

1.3.3 Correlation between environmental factors, physiochemical parameters and top genera

Significant correlations were identified between the most abundant genera and physiochemical parameters (Figure 1.3). Specifically, a considerable portion of the genera exhibited strong correlations with pH (pH_w, pH_KCl, pH_CaCl₂), CaCO₃, sum of bases (Bs), mean annual temperature (Temp), mean annual precipitation (Precip), exchangeable Ca (Caex), aggregates size distribution (Agsd_e, Agsd_d, Agsd_c), exchangeable Mg (Mgex), bioavailable Fe (Feba), available P (Pav), particulate organic C (POC), total N (Nt), organic matter content (OM), total organic C (TOC), and actual field moisture content (FMA). These findings suggest that these environmental parameters may play a crucial role in shaping the prokaryotic microbiome across the nine pedoclimatic regions, which further supports the results obtained by the NMDS analyses above.

1.3.4 Correlation between environmental factors, physiochemical parameters and functional gene abundance

Several of the physiochemical parameters were also found to correlate with the abundance of functional genes (Figure 1.4). Specifically, soil pH (pH_w, pH_KCl, pH_CaCl₂), CaCO₃, sum of bases (Bs), and mean annual temperature (Temp) exhibited negative correlations with all quantified functional genes. Conversely, positive correlations were observed for actual field moisture content (FMA), particulate organic C (POC), bioavailable Fe (Feba), electrical conductivity (EC), mean annual precipitation (Precip), organic matter content (OM), total organic C (TOC), total N (Nt), available P (Pav), NO₃, and bioavailable Zn (Znba). These results suggest that these factors may play a crucial role in defining microbial functionality. Additionally, the *amoA* gene, responsible for ammonia oxidation, strongly correlated with NO₂ content, aligning well with the fact that NO₂ is the end-product of ammonia oxidation (Rotthauwe *et al.*, 1997).

Figure 1.3. Spearman's rank correlations between environmental factors and top 40 most abundant genera. The strength of the correlations is indicated by color intensity and the asterisk indicates the significance level of the correlation * $p < 0.05$, ** $p < 0.01$, *** $p < 0.001$. Abbreviations: Mean annual temperature = Temp, Mean annual precipitation = Precip, Coarse sand = CSa, Fine sand = FSa, Coarse silt = CSi, Fine silt = FSi, Sand content = SA, Silt content = SI, Clay content = CL, pH in water = pH_w, pH in KCl = pH_KCl, pH in CaCl₂ = pH_CaCl₂, Electrical conductivity = EC, Organic Matter = OM, Total organic C = TOC, Particulate organic C = POC, Total N = Nt, Cation exchange capacity = CEC, Exchangeable Ca = Caex, Exchangeable Mg = Mgex, Exchangeable K = Kex, Exchangeable Na = Naex, Sum of bases = Bs, CaCO₃ = CaCO₃, Rock fragments and gravels = Rfg, Actual field moisture content = FMa, NH₄⁺ = NH₄, NO₃⁻ = NO₃, NO₂⁻ = NO₂, P available = Pav, Cu bioavailable = Cuba, Zn bioavailable = Znba, Fe bioavailable = Feba, Mn bioavailable = Mnba, Aggregates size distribution >2000 = Agsd_b, Aggregates size distribution 250-2000 = Agsd_c, Aggregates size distribution 53-250 = Agsd_d, Aggregates size distribution <53 = Agsd_e, Aggregates mean weight diameter = AMWD.

Figure 1.4. Spearman's rank correlations between environmental factors and functional gene abundances (gene copy number per g of soil). The strength of the correlations is indicated by color intensity and the asterisk indicates the significance level of the correlation * $p < 0.05$, ** $p < 0.01$, *** $p < 0.001$. Abbreviations: Mean annual temperature = Temp, Mean annual precipitation = Precip, Coarse sand = CSa, Fine sand = FSa, Coarse silt = CSi, Fine silt = FSi, Sand content = SA, Silt content = Si, Clay content = CL, pH in water = pH_w, pH in KCl = pH_KCl, pH in CaCl₂ = pH_CaCl₂, Electrical conductivity = EC, Organic Matter = OM, Total organic C = TOC, Particulate organic C = POC, Total N = Nt, Cation exchange capacity = CEC, Exchangeable Ca = Caex, Exchangeable Mg = Mgex, Exchangeable K = Kex, Exchangeable Na = Naex, Sum of bases = Bs, CaCO₃ = CaCO₃, Rock fragments and gravels = Rfg, Actual field moisture content = FMa, NH₄⁺ = NH₄, NO₃⁻ = NO₃, NO₂⁻ = NO₂, P available = Pav, Cu bioavailable = Cuba, Zn bioavailable = Znba, Fe bioavailable = Feba, Mn bioavailable = Mnba, Aggregates size distribution >2000 = Agsd_b, Aggregates size distribution 250-2000 = Agsd_c, Aggregates size distribution 53-250 = Agsd_d, Aggregates size distribution <53 = Agsd_e, Aggregates mean weight diameter = AMWD.

1.3.5 Associations between farming practices and prokaryotic genera

To investigate associations between different farming practices and microbial genera across regions, a differential abundance analysis was performed (Figure 1.5 and Figures A1.1-A1.5). The overall management system of the farms (organic vs. conventional farming) did not exhibit any significant association with any prokaryotic genera. In contrast, specific farming practices, such as the incorporation of remnant residual crops, crop rotation system, fertilization type, inclusion of legumes

in the crop rotation, and the use of pesticides, were found to be associated with several prokaryotic genera.

Figure 1.5. Number of genera differentially abundant between farming practice across all pedoclimatic regions. Farming practice included incorporation of residual crops into the soil (Residual crops; yes or no), crop rotation system (crop rotation; wheat-monoculture, short rotation (2-3 different crops), long rotation (>4 different crops)), type of fertilizer used (fertilizer; none, organic, mineral or organic+mineral), inclusion of legumes in crop rotation (Legumes; yes or no), Pesticides (none, herbicides, biocides, herbicides+fungicides, herbicides+fungicides+insecticides, fungicides, herbicides, insecticides+biocides) and tillage system (no tillage, deep inversion, deep mixing, or reduced tillage). Colors indicate the respective phylum of the detected genera.

Notably, the use of pesticides and crop rotation system exerted profound impacts on several genera. Particularly striking effects were observed when a combination of all types of pesticides (i.e., fungicide, herbicide, insecticide, and biocides) was employed in the field, leading to a remarkable increase in genera such as *Solirubrobacter*, *Nocardiodetes*, *Blastococcus*, *Skermanella*, and *Streptomyces*, while causing a decrease in other genera such as *Bradyrhizobium* (Figure A1.3). Concerning crop rotation systems, several genera were enhanced in fields with wheat monoculture production, including *Blastococcus*, *Rubrobacter*, *Skermanella*, *Streptomyces*, as well as several unassigned genera belonging to different phyla (Figure A1.1). Conversely, wheat monoculture production led to a reduction in less abundant taxa such as *Pseudomonas*, *Pedobacter*, *Arenimonas*, as well as other unassigned genera

Incorporation of residual crops and tillage practices also showed associations with various genera. For instance, incorporation of residual crops was linked to a decrease in genera such as *Solirubacter*, *Blastococcus*, *Streptomyces*, and *Candidatus Solibacter*, while a highly abundant unassigned genus belonging to *Betaproteobacteria* was significantly enriched (Figure A1.4.)

Regarding tillage systems, deep inversion was associated with a remarkable increase in genera such as *Blastococcus*, *Skermanella*, and others, while reduced or no tillage had an increasing impact on taxa such as *Geobacter*, as well as an unassigned member of *Xanthobacteriaceae* (Figure A1.5).

Overall, the results suggest that certain taxa, such as *Blastococcus*, *Skermanella*, *Streptomyces*, and *Solirubrobacter*, tend to be sensitive to farming practices, as variations in their abundance were associated with several of the farming practices. *Solirubrobacter* and *Blastococcus* have been reported to present advantages in stress resistance (Zhao *et al.*, 2022), which could explain their increased abundance in the case of pesticide use. *Streptomyces* are believed to be beneficial for crop production and disease management, emphasizing the importance of considering the impact of farming practices on their abundance (Rey and Dumas, 2017).

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2 Fungal diversity

2.1 Introduction

Fungi are considered as key organisms affecting major ecological processes, because they are inevitably important by contributing to the carbon and nutrient cycles, a good soil structure and disease control (Frąc et al., 2018). Decline of fungal mycelia may have caused depleted soil carbon pool and eventually reduce crop production on the arable fields established on deforested land (Lal 2004). Furthermore, management practices aiming to restore fungi and fungal energy channels likely prevent further degradation and carbon loss of arable soils (Morriën et al., 2017; Hannula & Morriën 2022). In fungal energy channel the nutrient and carbon cycle mediated by fungi represent “slow cycle” (Coleman et al. 1983) in which nutrients and carbon are retained in soil for longer to improve soil structure and functions towards more sustainable agriculture. Yet, there seems to be consensus that high ratios of fungi to bacteria usually lead to carbon accumulation and less CO₂ being released into the atmosphere (Bailey et al. 2002).

Functionally different fungi most likely have variable responses to changes in soil conditions. Saprotrophic soil fungi have a major role in decomposing soil organic matter and recycling of carbon and other nutrients (Turbé et al. 2010). In turn, AMF produce a sticky glomalin glycoprotein (Wright and Upadhyaya 1996), which forms aggregates with soil particles and makes them important in erosion control (Augé 2001, Caravaca et al. 2002, Rillig 2004a, Rillig 2004b, Rillig and Mummey 2006). In addition, AMF are also known to promote plant growth (Gianinazzi et al. 2010; Njeru et al. 2015; Cozzolino et al. 2016), protect plants from various diseases (Solaiman et al. 2014), and help plants to cope with water deficit (Bowles et al. 2016). However, the soil fungal community contains also harmful organisms which benefit from crop residues remaining on the soil surface. These include for example soil-borne phytopathogenic fungi such as species of genus *Fusarium* which are economically important pathogens of cereals and maize worldwide (Yli-Mattila 2010, Ferrigo et al. 2016). There are also lots of not so well-known fungi which can switch their lifestyle from free-living soil saprotrophs to endophytic fungi living inside their plant host as plant growth promoters (Weiß et al. 2016; Grabka et al. 2022). Thus, along with the promotion of plant growth and development, endophytes can also reduce oxidative stress of hosts and protect plants from pathogens and pests (White et al. 2019). Thus, by investigating what are the most intrinsic factors that impact fungal diversity and different fungal functional groups we are more able to estimate the role of fungi in arable fields and in promotion of sustainable agriculture.

Impacts of farming system and management practices on soil fungal community in nine different European pedoclimatic region were reported earlier in D3.3. However, also many abiotic factors specific for each regions, such as climatic factors (temperature, precipitation) and many soil parameters along with the management practice may result in changes in fungi. Here, we report how investigated soil features and climatic factors determined from wheat fields under conventional or

organic farming systems from nine pedoclimatic regions are linked to fungal richness, diversity, community composition and functional guilds.

2.2 Material and Methods

2.2.1 Sampling

Soils sampling in all nine regions were conducted according to the Handbook of WP3 ('Protocols for sampling, general soil characterization and soil biodiversity analysis', <http://soildiveragro.eu/publications/books/>) as previously reported in D3.3. Briefly, samples for DNA-based identification were taken as composite samples from two to three field sites within the same farm under organic and conventional farming system located in five different regional locations. Sub-samples targeting bacteria, fungi and nematodes were stored in freezer (-80°C) before they were shipped to DNA extraction and sequencing. Another set of samples for physical and chemical analyses were sieved and stored at room temperature or just dried before shipping in Spain.

2.2.2 DNA extractions, PCR and sequencing

The DNA extraction and amplicon sequencing was conducted according to protocol described in the Handbook (Lloret et al. 2020) and described in the previously published D3.3 report.

2.2.3 Bioinformatics

Bioinformatics for the fungal ITS sequence data was conducted with PipeCraft open-source toolkit for bioinformatics analysis (Anslan et al. 2017) as described in the previously published D3.3 report.

2.2.4 Statistics

Most of the analyses were determined in R version 3.6.0 or 3.6.1 (R core Team 2018) and R studio (version 1.2.5001). All figures were made using R-pckage 'ggplot2' (Wickham 2016). Alpha-diversity, richness as observed number of OTUs and Chao1 estimate, and diversity using Shannon and InverseSimpson indexes were obtained from 'microbiome' R package (Lahti et al. 2017), and they were determined from the raw data. Beta-diversity was investigated with non-metric

multidimensional scaling (NMDS) from the relative abundance of reads (proportions from the total read amounts in the sample library). NMDS was conducted with stable solution from random starts, axis scaling and species scores with function metaMDS in 'vegan' package 2.5-5 (Oksanen et al. 2019) by using Bray-Curtis dissimilarity index. Soil parameters from soil chemical and physical data were used in NMDS as environmental factors to investigate their effects on the variation on fungal OTU composition. FUNGuild, the online application tool, was used to detect functional information, fungal guilds of OTUs (Nguyen et al., 2016).

The mixed model analyses were performed with the GLIMMIX procedure of the SAS statistical software (version 9.4). Linear mixed models (LMMs) and generalized linear mixed models (GLMMs) were used in analyses. Soil parameters from soil chemical and physical data, data from management practices and climatic factors listed were used as explanatory variables. Mixed models were used to account for correlation of observations (similarity of response variable values). Normally distributed response variables were analysed by LMMs. Response variables with right skewed distribution (proportionally more small than large values) and value restrictions (values > 0 or in range 0-1 or values were counts) were analysed by GLMMs using gamma, binomial or negative binomial distribution assumption. Response variables of the models were: 1) alpha diversity indices and 2) proportions of fungal functional guilds (saprotrophs, symbiotrophs, pathotrophs). At first stage, pedoclimatic region, management (conventional or organic) and their interaction were used as explanatory (fixed) factors. Location was used as random factor to account for correlation of field observations. At second stage, to find more exact explanatory factors instead of pedoclimatic region, it was moved to random factor together with location. Farming system was left as fixed factor. The Tukey-Kramer method was used in pairwise comparisons of class means for categorical fixed factors. For generalizing the modelling results to the data population, the average model predictions with their 95% confidence intervals were calculated using only the explanatory (fixed) factors.

The effect of potential predictors on OTUs were investigated within pedoclimatic regions with cluster analysis. Clr-transformed OTU data using the Ward method was applied which detected two clearly separated groups. Potential predictors were used to model the probability of belonging to a specific cluster group using a logistic regression model. Modeling followed a machine learning approach to maximize the predictive ability of the model. A set of potential predictors were defined from soil chemical and physical data and from management practices, and used a grid search approach, where every predictor combination was considered. For every predictor combination, we applied leave-one-out cross-validation to calculate the cross-validation (CV) accuracy. The best model was considered the one for which the CV accuracy was maximized. For the best model, we applied bootstrapping (using the full data) and out of bag prediction in order to obtain error bounds for the accuracy.

2.3 Results

2.3.1 Factors affecting fungal alpha diversity

Fungal richness was generally higher under organic farming and correlated positively with higher long-term precipitation, and negatively with mean lowest 12-month temperatures, carbonate content and available P (Table 2.1). Model also showed that exchangeable calcium amount separately or together with farming system were significant predictors for both Shannon and Inverse Simpson indices. Also nitrate amount was significant predictor for Shannon index. Shannon and Inverse Simpson indices increase under conventional farming with increasing exchangeable calcium amount and Shannon index decrease with increasing nitrate content.

TABLE 2.1

VARIABLE	RICHNESS		CHAO1		SHANNON		SIMPSON	
	F	<i>p</i>	F	<i>p</i>	F	<i>p</i>	F	<i>p</i>
System	6.59	0.01	6.28	0.01	6.32	0.01	8.71	0.004
MeanPre_30Yrs	6.40	0.01	6.65	0.01				
MeanT_12Mon	4.77	0.03	4.76	0.03				
CaCO3	6.12	0.02	9.72	0.002				
Pav	8.95	0.004	10.95	0.001				
NO3					11.52	0.001		
Caex					4.15	0.04		
Caex X System					6.89	0.01	4.78	0.03

Table 2.1. Results from the linear mixed model testing the effects of management practices, climatic and soil physical and chemical parameters on fungal alpha-diversity measures. Differences are considered significant at $P < 0.05$. Abbreviations: MeanPrec_30Yrs, mean long-term precipitation for 30 years period before sampling, precipitation; MeanT_12Mon, mean temperature for 12 months before sampling; CaCO₃, carbonate content as % in soil; Pav, available phosphorus as mg kg⁻¹ in dry soil; NO₃, nitrate as mg kg⁻¹ in dry soil; Caex, exchangeable calcium as cmol kg⁻¹ in dry soil.

2.3.2 Factors affecting fungal OTU composition (beta diversity)

There were clear differences in soil fungal OTU composition between different regions as already stated in D3.3 report (Figure 2.1). Soil pH, CaCO₃ content, silt content, bulk density and C:N ratio were significant environmental factors indicating towards the fungal OTU composition of the Pannonian region. Clay content, in turn, pointed more towards that of the Mediterranean regions. In turn, bioavailable phosphorus (Pav) pointed towards the Lusitanian region. In addition, sand content, mean weight of soil aggregates (AMWD), NO₃ content, particulate soil carbon content (POC) and field moisture content (FMa) towards fungal OTU composition of the other five regions (two Atlantic, Continental, Nemoral and Boreal).

Figure 2.1. NMDS ordination from the fungal ITS derived OTU data. Different colours separate OTUs by regions and symbols by farming management systems (conv, conventional; org, organic). Ellipses show the confidence intervals of the mean according to separations by regions. Vectors represent significant environmental variables affecting the composition ($p < 0.05$).

2.3.3 Factors affecting functional fungal guilds

According to the model, there was a significant effect of landform on saprotrophic fungal guild (Table 2.2). There was higher proportion of saprotrophs in hills with 5-25% slope compared to that detected from the piedmonts or fans with 1-5 % slope. However, the proportions of pathotrophs and symbiotrophs were so small that reliable generalized linear model could not be produced from the data.

TABLE 2.2

VARIABLE	F	P
Farming System	0.78	0.38
Landform	18.26	<0.0001

Table 2.2. Results from the generalized linear mixed model showing the significant explanatory variables for predicting the proportion of saprotrophic fungi. Differences are considered significant at $P < 0.05$.

2.3.4 Factors affecting the abundance of fungal OTUs

Cluster analysis with machine learning approach revealed partly same explanatory factors affecting OTU abundances in different regions such as soil pH and bulk density in 0-10 cm depth (Table 2.3). Bulk density in the 0-10 cm depth was the most important (rank 1) factor affecting the abundance of OTUs in clusters in North Atlantic, Boreal, North Mediterranean and Nemoral regions. Higher bulk density predicts the increasing abundance of pathogenic *Nectriaceae* and *Alternaria* in the North Mediterranean region. Higher mean soil aggregate size and soil pH predicts the increasing abundance of pathogenic *Mycophaerella* and *Nectriaceae* in the South Mediterranean region. Soil pH was one of the most important predictors of the OTU abundances in four regions. Higher soil pH predicts the increasing abundance of *Acremonium* and decreasing abundance of pathogenic *Fusarium* both in Central Atlantic and Nemoral regions. Higher soluble phosphorus content predicts, for instance, decreasing amounts of *M. elongata* and pathogenic *Fusarium* in the Lusitanian region, and increasing abundance of *Acremonium* and *M. alpina*, and decreasing abundance of *M. horticola* in the Nemoral region. Higher soil organic matter content and absence of legumes in crop rotation predicted increasing abundance of *Acremonium* in the Continental region. In the most northern boreal region, bulk density in 0-10 cm depth was the most important predictors followed by soil moisture and soil pH predicting increasing of abundances of *Saitozyma* and *M. elongata*, and decreasing abundances of *Solicoccozyma* and *M. horticola*. In turn, whether organic farming was practiced it affected the conversely on those taxa.

Results showed that the abundance of OTUs affiliating to *Mortierella* was very often linked to various factors in soils of the many regions. Fungi of genus *Mortierella* are generally defined as widespread saprotrophs with ability to survive under various environmental conditions and capable of utilizing variety of carbon sources containing cellulose, hemicellulose and chitin. Some strains also belong to plant growth-promoting fungi (PGPF) that help plants to access to the bioavailable forms of P and Fe, product phytohormones and protect plants from pathogens (Ozimek & Hanaka 2021). Thus, our results indicate that species of *Mortierella* can be used as an indicator group responding to changes in soil conditions such in soil pH, bulk density or available phosphorus in wheat fields of many European regions. Furthermore, results suggest that some pathogens (*Fusarium*, *Alternaria*,

Nectriaceae) may increase with increasing bulk density in the surface soil and soil pH especially in the Mediterranean regions.

TABLE 2.3

REGION	Exp factor	Model estim	Imp rank	CL_0 OTU (%)	CL_1 OTU (%)	Fungal taxa	guild
Atl_cent	soil pH	-3.0	1	39	24	<i>Acremonium</i>	PatSapSym
	BD 0-10cm	16.4	2	6	3	<i>Pseudeurotium</i>	Sap
	sand (%)	0.05	3	0	5	<i>Saitozyma</i>	?
				2	9	<i>Fusarium</i>	Pat
Atl_north	BD 0-10 cm	10.2	1	8	15	<i>Tetragoniomyces</i>	?
	OM (%)	1.1	2	4	0.4	<i>Solicoccozyma</i>	?
	clay (%)	1.5	3				
Boreal	BD 0-10 cm	-47.3	1	13	5	<i>Saitozyma</i>	?
	soil moist (%)	-0.99	2	13	1	<i>Mortierella^{a)}</i>	?
	soil pH	-3.3	3	4	8	<i>Solicoccozyma</i>	?
	org farming	2.0	4	4	16	<i>Mortierella^{b)}</i>	SapSym
Cont	no legumes	-3.9	1	43	25	<i>Acremonium</i>	PatSapSym
	OM (%)	-1.5	2	4	1	<i>Lasiosphaeriaceae</i>	Sap
				1	6	<i>Mortierella^{a)}</i>	SapSym
				-	0.5	6	<i>Endophoma</i>
Lusit	soluble P (%)	0.04	1	17	0	<i>Pseudaleuria</i>	SapSym
	clay (%)	0.35	2	12	0	<i>Humicola</i>	?
				4	14	<i>Mortierella^{a)}</i>	SapSym
				5	16	<i>Fusarium</i>	Pat
Med_north	BD 0-10 cm	-6.9		9	1	<i>Nectriaceae</i>	Pat
				7	0.1	<i>Alternaria</i>	Pat
				0	5	<i>Mortierella^{a)}</i>	SapSym
				0.1	6	<i>Pleosporales</i>	?
Med_south	soil aggr. size	-8.7	1	14	2	<i>Mycosphaerella</i>	Pat
	clay (%)	1.0	2	7	0	<i>Nectriaceae</i>	Pat
	soil pH	-6.5	3	0	4	<i>Preussia</i>	Sap
				3	10	<i>Botryotrichum</i>	Sap
Nemoral	BD 0-10 cm	-7.9	1	21	9	<i>Acremonium</i>	PatSapSym

	soluble P	-0.02	2	4	0.4	<i>Mortierella</i> ^{c)}	SapSym
				33	37	<i>Mortierella</i> ^{b)}	SapSym
Pann	soil pH	4.7		10	2	<i>Solicoccozyma</i>	?
				9	4	<i>Fusarium</i>	Pat
				0	3	<i>Sordariomycetes</i>	?
				9	15	<i>Acremonium</i>	PatSapSym

Table 2.3. The results of the cluster analysis. Negative or positive model estimates for the best explanatory factors indicates higher probability to belong to cluster 0 or cluster 1 with importance ranks (range: 1, the most important; 4, the least important) by regions, respectively. Relative proportions of four OTUs with biggest difference between clusters (at least 2.0 % difference), their taxonomic affiliations (according to species hypothesis at genus level if possible) and functional guilds according to FunGuild are shown. a) *M. elongata*, b) *M. horticola*, c) *M. alpine*.

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3 Microbial biomass

3.1 Introduction

Soil microbial biomass or abundance is a very relevant parameter in relation to soil health, given the essential role of microorganisms in numerous soil functions, including organic matter decomposition, nutrient cycling and biodiversity (Nannipieri et al., 2003; González-Quiñones et al., 2011). The biomass, or abundance, can be interpreted as a measurement of the microbial “reservoir” in soils. Hence, the maintenance and/or increase of this parameter in soils is of significant importance for agricultural sustainability.

Microbial abundance can be approached from different perspectives: total microbial abundance or abundance of specific groups, such as bacteria or fungi. The microbial abundance can be estimated using different methodologies (Zelles et al., 1994, Martens, 1995). One common methodology is the extraction of lipids specific of different groups of microorganisms, such as phospholipid fatty acids (PLFAs) (Frostegård and Bååth, 1996) or neutral lipid fatty acids (NLFAs) (Ngosong et al., 2012), that are being employed in SoildiverAgro project.

3.2 Material and Methods

3.2.1 Soil sampling

Soil sampling in the nine pedoclimatic regions studied was performed following Handbook WP3 (Protocols for sampling general soil characterization and soil biodiversity analysis, <http://soildiveragro.eu/publications/books/>), as previously detailed in D3.3 (Report on biodiversity status of soil microorganisms and soil fauna across the major European pedoclimatic regions). In summary, soil composite samples for microbial abundance were collected from two or three sites within the same farm under organic and conventional farming systems, across five different regional locations. Once in the laboratory, each composite sample was air dried at room temperature, sieved by < 2 mm and stored in polypropylene containers until analysis.

3.2.2 Microbial biomass/abundance determination

The abundance of different groups of microbes was estimated following Frostegård and Bååth (1996) method. In brief:

1. Lipids extraction from soil using “Bligh and Dyer” solution, and separation among neutral lipids, glycolipids and phospholipids using silica columns and solvents with different polarity: methanol for neutral lipids, acetone for glycolipids and chloroform for phospholipids.
2. Once separated, neutral lipids and phospholipids were subjected to mild alkaline methanolysis (transesterification) to break the lipids and obtain the fatty acids. Later, the fatty acids were determined by gas chromatography.
3. Different fatty acids are specific of different microbial groups, allowing to determine the abundance of each group by summing different fatty acids. The majority of microbial groups were estimated utilising phospholipid fatty acids (PLFAs) while neutral lipid fatty acid (NLFA) 16:1 ω 5 was used to estimate the abundance of arbuscular mycorrhizal fungi (Table 3.1).

In order to linearly correlate and visualize environmental parameters and microbial biomass, a redundancy analysis (RDA) was performed in R version 4.0.2 (R Core Team 2020) and R studio (version 1.3.1073) using the ‘vegan’ (Oksanen et al. 2019) package. Environmental parameters were previously standardized with the function “deconstand()”. Forward selection using the ordiR2step function of the “vegan” R package was conducted to simplify the model by selecting environmental factors which were statistically most important for the model. In the RDA plot, only the most significant ($p < 0.05$) of the forward-selected environmental factors and pH, were included.

TABLE 3.1	
TOTAL ABUNDANCE	ALL DETERMINED PLFAS
Bacteria	PLFAS: i15:0, a15:0, 15:0, i16:0, 16:1 ω 9, 16:1 ω 7t, i17:0, a17:0, 17:0, cy17:0, 18:1 ω 7, cy19:0
Gram-positive Bacteria	PLFAS: br17:0, br18:0, i17:0, i16:0, i16:1, 10Me16:0, 10Me17:0, i15:0, a15:0, 16:1 ω 9, 16:1 ω 7c, 18:1 ω 7, 19:1
Gram-negative Bacteria	PLFAS: cy17:0, cy19:0, r-hydroxy fatty acids, 16:1 ω 9, 16:1 ω 7, 16:1 ω 5, 18:1 ω 7, 19:1
Actinobacteria	PLFAS: 10Me16:0, 10Me17:0, 10Me18:0
Fungi	PLFAS: 18:2 ω 6 (linoleic acid)
Arbuscular mycorrhizal fungi	NLFAS: 16:1 ω 5

Table 3.1. Fatty acid biomarkers used to estimate the abundance of different microbial groups.

3.3 Results

3.3.1 Relationship between environmental factors, physiochemical parameters and soil microbial abundance

Figure 3.1 shows the results of the redundancy analysis (RDA) performed between microbial abundance and different environmental factors, both for organic and conventional farming systems. The RDA1 axis accounts for 74% of the variability in the data, indicating that most of the environmental factors influencing microbial abundance are represented on this axis. Conversely, RDA2 axis accounts for only 0.4% of the data variability, indicating that the environmental factors represented on it provide additional information, but to a lesser extent than RDA1 axis.

Soil organic matter (OM), total organic carbon (TOC), bioavailable Fe (Fe_{ba}) and the mean annual precipitation in the last 12 months (P₁₂) showed a robust positive correlation with RDA1, and also a positive correlation with RDA2, indicating a significant influence of these factors on the variations in microbial abundance. Conversely, soil pH in water (pH_w) and the average minimum temperatures in the last 12 months (T_{min}) demonstrated an inverse strong correlation with the RDA1 axis. Therefore, pH_w and T_{min} are also shaping the microbial community. The RDA analysis also showed that other environmental factors, such as bioavailable Zn (Zn_{ba}), rock fragments (R_{fg}) and bulk density 10 – 25 cm (BD₁₀₋₂₅), sand content (SA) and aggregates mean weight diameter (AMWD) contributed to the microbial biomass variations, but to a lesser extent.

Some groups of soil samples from different regions presented slight clustering. For example, soil samples from the Mediterranean North and South regions were more situated to the left of the RDA1 axis, which suggests a correlation with the environmental factors associated with RDA1. Other pedoclimatic regions also presented a slight clustering, such as Pannonian or Atlantic North.

Regarding the influence of the system farming, a slight clustering was only observed for the conventional samples from the Lusitanian region, so there was not an apparent effect of the system farming on the microbial abundance.

Figure 3.1. Redundancy analysis between microbial biomass and environmental parameters of the analyzed fields and soil samples. Each point in the plot represents microbial biomass of a specific field. The shape of the points indicates field agricultural management: conventional (circle) or organic (triangle). The length of the arrows represents the strength of the correlation between microbial biomass and environmental properties. Abbreviations: Fe bioavailable = Feba, total organic carbon = TOC, organic matter content = OM, mean annual precipitation in the last 12 months = P12, rock fragments and gravels = Rfg, Zn bioavailable = Znba, pH in water = pHw, aggregates mean weight diameter = AMWD, bulk density from 10 to 25 cm = BD_10-25, sand content = SA, average minimum temperatures in the last 12 months = Tmin.

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4 Nematode diversity

4.1 Introduction

Nematodes play diverse roles in agricultural ecosystems, comprising various trophic groups such as bacterivores, fungivores, predators, omnivores, and herbivores (Ferris et al., 2001). Understanding the drivers and pressures acting on complete nematode communities is essential for effective management strategies aimed at sustaining soil health and crop productivity. In recent literature it has been reported that different practices within agricultural management systems, as well as soil characteristics including texture, pH, organic matter content, and nutrient levels, may play an important role in shaping the biodiversity of nematodes (Berkelmans et al., 2003; Bongiorno et al., 2019; Cheng et al., 2021). Different nematode trophic groups exhibit preferences for specific soil conditions. For instance, bacterivorous nematodes thrive in soils rich in organic matter, while fungal-feeding nematodes are more abundant in habitats with high fungal biomass (Ferris & Bongers, 2006). Plant diversity and crop management strategies significantly affect nematode communities in agricultural fields. Crop rotation, cover cropping, and intercropping practices can alter the availability of food resources for nematodes, leading to shifts in community composition (Culman et al., 2009; Diakhaté et al., 2013, DuPont et al., 2009). Diverse cropping systems tend to support more complex nematode communities with a balance of trophic groups. Climatic factors such as temperature, humidity, and precipitation patterns influence nematode activity, reproduction, and survival (Ankrom et al., 2022). Different nematode species have specific temperature optima for growth and development. Changes in climate regimes can alter nematode distribution patterns, affecting community dynamics and ecosystem functioning in agricultural soils. The use of agrochemicals, including fertilizers, pesticides, and herbicides, can exert selective pressures on nematode communities (Eisenhauer et al., 2010). Some chemicals may directly impact nematode populations, while others indirectly affect nematode communities by altering soil microbial communities or crop health. Sustainable agricultural practices aim to minimize negative impacts on nematode biodiversity while promoting soil health (Freckman & Ettema, 1993; Neher, 2010; Quist et al., 2016).

In Deliverable D3.3, the analysis was conducted according to a systems research approach. In this report we describe about the interrelation of the obtained nematode communities and different data-sets such as climatic factors (temperature, precipitation), many soil parameters and farming operations linked to the selected management practices (conventional and organic farming). The analysis aims at pinpointing the most important factors influencing nematode populations.

4.2 Material and Methods

4.2.1 Nematode community characterization

As explained in Deliverable Report D3.3, nematode communities were extracted from 188 soil samples following a conventional or organic management system by zonal centrifugation (Hendrickx, 1995). The obtained nematode suspension was analyzed molecularly by DNA-metabarcoding (V6-V8 region of the 18S rRNA gene sequencing). Briefly, DNA was extracted using a DNA-extraction kit with few modifications, the quality and concentration of the DNA was checked with a UV-spectrophotometer and fluorometer respectively, and a library prep was made from each nematode DNA extract by applying a 2-step amplification process. Amplicon libraries with sample-specific indices were pooled in equimolar amounts according to the instructions provided by the sequence service and sequenced on an Illumina MiSeq PE300 platform (2 x 300 bp). After receiving the raw sequence data from the sequence service provider, the data was analyzed and quality checked. The retained sequences were characterized by comparing them with an in-house curated custom NCBI reference nematode sequence database. A more detailed description of this procedure can be found in the Handbook of WP3 ('Protocols for sampling, general soil characterization and soil biodiversity analysis', <http://soildiveragro.eu/publications/books/>) and the Deliverable report D3.3.

4.2.2 Nematode community analysis

The same (statistical) analysis methods as described in Deliverable report D3.3 were used to relate the nematode biological and functional diversity to different datasets. NMDS ordinations and Permanova were applied to visualise and calculate the significance of physical and chemical soil characters (see Deliverable report D3.2), climatological and agricultural management factors on the nematode biodiversity. Food web analyses based on nematode functional guilds provide a powerful tool for analyzing functional diversity. By classifying nematodes into groups based on their feeding habits and life strategies, researchers can gain insights into the health and complexity of the soil ecosystem linked to agricultural treatments. For instance, a high abundance of bacterivore and fungivore nematodes indicates a strong base of decomposers, while an increase in predator nematodes suggests a well-established food web with higher trophic levels (Bongers and Ferris, 1999). For all statistical comparisons, p-values below 0.05 were considered statistically significant.

4.3 Results

4.3.1 Effects of environmental factors

In this study, environmental factors comprises the climatological, physical and chemical data sets. Some of them significantly influenced the nematode communities, however, there is no clear correlation with the farming system, conventional or organic (Figure 4.1 and 4.2). Some of the factors were reported before in literature and thus are reconfirmed like pH (pH_w, pH_{KCl}, pH_{CaCl₂}) (Korthals et al., 1996), texture (silt, sand, coarse silt) and organic matter (Quist et al., 2019). Others are new (like bioavailable Mn, Zn).

It can be noticed that climatological factors like precipitation (Prec30Y and Prec12M) and temperature (Temp30Y, Temp12M and TempHigh) are important factors influencing nematode communities (Figure 4.1 and 4.2). In relation to this, the field moisture content (FMa) also is mentioned as an impacting factor. This is not surprising as soil nematodes are considered aquatic organisms, living inside the waterfilm surrounding soil particles. Obviously, water availability and linked nematode abundance and diversity was very much influenced by the climate and weather conditions in the different regions at the time of the sampling. These findings have been reported before not only for nematodes but many other soil organisms as well.

4.3.2 Effects of management practices

Deliverable report D3.3 concluded that the nematode biodiversity is directed more by the region with its specific conditions concerning climate and soil characteristics, then by the farming systems. Due to this reason, the relationship between the nematode communities and the different management practices conducted in each farming system was investigated per region to avoid interference of the climatological factors. In table 4.1 the statistically significant management practices are listed per region. It can be noticed that in 2 regions (Boreal and Mediterranean North) none of the management practices influenced the nematode communities significantly. In the other regions the differential use of phytoproducts always, with exception of Mediterranean South, caused a significant impact on the nematode community, in some cases even the highest impact (Continental, Lusitanian and Pannonian) (fig. 4.3). Next to phytoproducts, also different fertility management methods caused considerable shifts in nematode communities. In some regions this treatment showed even the highest impact on nematode communities (Atlantic Central, Atlantic North, and Nemoral) (fig. 4.4). Also the crop rotation system (the highest impact in the Mediterranean South region) and tillage practices often resulted in a significant impact.

Figure 4.1. NMDS ordination from the nematode 18S rRNA derived ASV data. Different colours separate ASVs by farming management systems (Conv, conventional; Org, organic). Ellipses show the confidence intervals of the mean according to separations by the farming system. Vectors represent significant environmental variables affecting the composition ($p < 0.05$). SI = silt, SA = sand, Csi = Coarse silt, pH_w = pH measured in water, pH_KCl = Ph measured in KCl, pH_CaCl₂ = pH measured in CaCl₂, MnBa = bioavailable Manganese, Pav = available phosphor, ZnBa = bioavailable Zinc, FMa = field moisture content, CaCO₃ = calcium carbonate, TOC = total organic carbon, POC = particulate organic carbon, Nt = total nitrogen, EC = electric conductivity, OM = organic matter, Temp30Y = mean temperature during the last 30 years, Temp12M = mean temperature during the last 12 months, TempHigh = average of maximum temperature of the last 12 months prior to the sampling event, Prec30Y = mean precipitation during the last 30 years, Prec12M = mean precipitation during the last 12 months.

Figure 4.2. NMDS ordination from the nematode 18S rRNA derived ASV data. Different colours separate ASVs by region (Atl_cent = Atlantic Central, Atl_north = Atlantic North, Cont = Continental, Lusit = Lusitanian, Med_north = Mediterranean North, Med_south = Mediterranean South, Pann = Pannonian). Ellipses show the confidence intervals of the mean according to separations by the region. Vectors represent significant environmental variables affecting the composition ($p < 0.05$). SI = silt, SA = sand, Csi = Coarse silt, pH_w = pH measured in water, pH_KCl = Ph measured in KCl, pH_CaCl₂ = pH measured in CaCl₂, MnBa = bioavailable Manganese, Pav = available phosphor, ZnBa = bioavailable Zinc, FMa = field moisture content, CaCO₃ = calcium carbonate, TOC = total organic carbon, POC = particulate organic carbon, Nt = total nitrogen, EC = electric conductivity, OM = organic matter, Temp30Y = mean temperature during the last 30 years, Temp12M = mean temperature during the last 12 months, TempHigh = average of maximum temperature of the last 12 months prior to the sampling event, Prec30Y = mean precipitation during the last 30 years, Prec12M = mean precipitation during the last 12 months.

TABLE 4.1

REGION	MANAGEMENT PRACTISE	R2	F	PR(>F)
Atlantic Central	Fert	0,20334	1,7016	0,003
	Phyto	0,15694	1,9546	0,002
	Till	0,18573	1,5206	0,019
Atlantic North	CRS	0,09126	1,8077	0,031
	Fert	0,20271	2,1612	0,002
	Phyto	0,19117	2,0091	0,002
	Till	0,18338	4,042	0,001
Boreal	-			
Continental	CRS	0,13929	2,7511	0,002
	Phyto	0,23567	2,4667	0,001
	Till	0,19349	1,9192	0,003
Lusitanian	Fert	0,24682	2,6216	0,002
	Phyto	0,28298	1,9733	0,006
	Till	0,13938	2,7531	0,007
Mediterranean North	-			
Mediterranean South	CRS	0,16341	3,1251	0,038
Nemoral	CRS	0,07323	1,4223	0,032
	Fert	0,2234	1,5342	0,001
	Phyto	0,15185	1,5218	0,002
	Till	0,20536	1,3783	0,003
Pannonian	Fert	0,28359	1,9793	0,001
	Phyto	0,42445	1,9175	0,001
	Till	0,16527	1,5839	0,016

Table 4.1. Permanova data of the statistically significant practices per region (see also fig. 3, 4 and 5). R2 (R-squared) is a goodness-of-fit measure (1 = perfect fit). F = F-value to assess the significance of the main effect. Pr = PerMANOVA p-value to indicate the significance of the main effect. A p-value less than 0.05 suggests that the group differences are statistically significant. Fert = fertilization method; Phyto = phytosanitary measurements, Till = tillage practices; CRS = crop rotation system.

Figure 4.3. NMDS ordination from the nematode 18S rRNA derived ASV data. Different symbols represent the farming systems (Conv = conventional farming, Org = organic farming). Different colours separate ASVs by the differential application of phytosanitary measurements (Combi = combination of phytoproducts; H = Herb = Herbicides, F = Fungicides, I = Insecticides, N = Nematicides, B = biocides, None = no phytoproduct applied). Upper left panel = Continental region, upper right panel = Lusitanian region, lower panel = Pannonian region). Ellipses show the confidence intervals of the mean according to separations by the factor.

Figure 4.4. NMDS ordination from the nematode 18S rRNA derived ASV data. Different symbols represent the farming systems (Conv = conventional farming, Org = organic farming,). Different colours separate ASVs by the differential fertilisation methods (Min= mineral fertilisation; Org = Organic fertilisation, None = no fertilisation sources used). Upper left panel = Continental region, upper right panel = Lusitanian region, lower panel = Pannonian region). Ellipses show the confidence intervals of the mean according to separations by the factor.

4.3.3 Effects on functional diversity

The food web analysis, which is based on the nematode-specific structure and enrichment indexes (SI and EI), can reveal whether the different farming systems improved or deteriorated the soil health condition. In table A4.1 till 4 both index values and corresponding standard deviation and p-values is reported considering the most important farming practices (crop rotation system, tillage methods, fertility methods and usage of phytoproducts). Only in a handful occasions the indexes were significantly changed ($p < 0.05$) pointing to a significant effect on nematode functional diversity. In the Atlantic-North region the tillage and fertility methods as well as application of phyto-products had a significant effect on both indexes EI and SI (fig. 4.5). Clearly, results suggest that application of mineral fertilizers and phytoproducts causes a less healthy soil condition compared to organic or no fertilizer and no usage of phytoproducts. On the other hand it is surprising to see that the 'Deepmix' tillage method has a more negative effect on functional diversity compared to 'DeepInv'. A similar conclusion concerning the tillage methods in the Nemoral region can be formulated (fig. 4.5). It is surprising and difficult to explain that only the method 'RedInv' would result in a less functional diverse nematode community compared to the other methods applied. In the Lusitanian region also the fertility methods and the application of phytoproducts caused a significant shift in the functional diversity of the nematode communities (fig. 4.5). Since we cannot always explain these shifts, possibly other factors play a more important role. However, it is clear that organic fertilization results in a higher Enrichment Index compared to mineral fertilization. A higher EI points towards a more diverse presence of solely bacterivores and/or fungivores which on its turn points towards the presence of plenty of bacteria and/or fungi which feed on the added organic mass.

Figure 4.5. Food Web Analysis (SI = Structure Index versus EI = Enrichment Index) of the tillage and fertility methods and the application of phytoproducts in the Atlantic-North region ($p < 0.05$). Phytoproducts: H = Herbicides, F = Fungicides, I = Insecticides, None = no phytoproduct applied; Tillage: DeepInv = conventional

tillage - deep soil inversion (ploughing till a depth of 15-35 cm, typically 25 cm), DeepMix = reduced tillage - deep soil mixing without inversion (cultivator, spader, rotavader till a depth of 15-35 cm, typically 25 cm).

Figure 4.6. Food Web Analysis (SI = Structure Index versus EI = Enrichment Index) of the tillage methods in the Nemoral region ($p < 0.05$). Tillage: DeepInv = conventional tillage - deep soil inversion (ploughing till a depth of 15-35 cm, typically 25 cm), RedInv = conventional tillage - shallow soil inversion (shallow ploughing/disc harrowing till a depth of 10-12 cm, No = no mixing or inversion of the soil (direct seeding, subsoiler), RedMix = reduced tillage – shallow soil mixing without inversion (harrow other than disc harrow till a depth of 10-12 cm).

Figure 4.6. Food Web Analysis (SI = Structure Index versus EI = Enrichment Index) of the tillage methods in the Lusitanian region ($p < 0.05$). Phytoproducts: H = Herbicides, F = Fungicides, I = Insecticides, None = no phytoproduct applied.

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5 Earthworm diversity

5.1 Introduction

Earthworms are key members of soil fauna communities with functional roles as physical and chemical engineers by modifying soil structure and regulating nutrient cycles and as biological regulators shaping soil biota communities (Turbé et al., 2010). In agricultural soils they contribute to maintenance of favorable soil conditions (Bertrand et al., 2015) and are known to increase crop yields, mainly through the enhancement of nutrient cycling (van Groenigen et al., 2014).

Three main ecological groups of earthworms can be distinguished (*sensu* Bouché, 1977): epigeic litter dwelling species, endogeic mineral-soil burrowers, and anecic, vertically burrowing species which often feed on plant residues on the soil surface. In addition, there are intermediate categories, such as e.g. epiendogeic species that are positioned between epigeics and endogeics. This ecological and functional variation signifies the manifold relevance of earthworms in the soil system and the varying responses of earthworm species to changes in the soil environment. Frequency and intensity of agricultural management (e.g. tillage), quality of chemical and other inputs (agrochemicals and manures) together with types of crops and their rotation are among the factors affecting earthworm species diversity and abundance (Whalen and Sampedro, 2010; Bai et al., 2018). These factors have long-lasting impacts on earthworm communities with legacy effects from previous crops (e.g. remaining residues) and land uses (Lago et al., 2020). Arable systems often persist in an early stage of succession due to the seasonal sequence of seeding, cultivation and harvest which often impedes the development of species-rich earthworm communities. The typically low within field (alpha) diversity of arable soil earthworms (Phillips et al., 2019) and the absence of certain ecological groups under the most intensive systems (Briones and Schmidt, 2017) also is a strong indication of the health condition of the agricultural system in terms of soil functions. Furthermore, climate controls the earthworm community structure. A European wide evaluation of earthworm surveys have shown geographical patterns in species distributions within regions on the European scale (Rutgers et al. 2016). On the global scale, it has been demonstrated that precipitation strongly affects species richness, abundance and biomass of earthworms (Phillips et al. 2019).

The aim of this study was to assess the impacts of conventional and organic farming on earthworm communities in nine pedoclimatic regions of Europe to elucidate how the local soil and environmental conditions as well as agricultural management shape their communities. The first phase of the study looked at the large-scale geographical patterns and at differences between agricultural practices (organic and conventional farming) (Deliverable report D3.3). This second phase focuses at the effects of additional environmental and agricultural factors.

5.2 Material and Methods

5.2.1 Sampling and morphological identification

At each of the nine pedoclimatic regions, 10 wheat producing fields of conventional and organic management practices were sampled. The sampling was conducted according to the Handbook of WP3 ('Protocols for sampling, general soil characterization and soil biodiversity analysis', <http://soildiveragro.eu/publications/books/>) as previously reported in D3.3. Important to keep in mind is that in most regions the samples were taken between August and November 2019 depending on weather conditions, however, the two Mediterranean regions and the Pannonian region were sampled half and one year later respectively to avoid extreme drought conditions and high temperatures, which characterized many parts of Europe in 2019.

All earthworms collected were identified individually by microscopic examination and their the biomass recorded. In previous mentioned Handbook of WP3 and in Deliverable report D3.3, a description of this procedure and the data obtained can be found.

5.2.2 Statistical analysis

The mixed model analyses of the data - using GLIMMIX procedure of SAS© - was done essentially the same way as explained above for the analyses of fungi data (chapter 2.2.4). The earthworm metrics were total density (individuals m⁻²), fresh mass (g m⁻²), species number (richness) and proportions of juveniles and the endogeic and anecic groups

5.3 Results

5.3.1 Statistical conclusions

There were no statistically discernible differences in the two earthworm community metrics between conventionally and organically managed fields although some indicative differences in the mean values were detected (Table 5.1; Deliverable report D3.3). Accordingly, there was a statistically significant geographical trend with the highest values at the northernmost region (Boreal) and the lowest values at the southernmost region (Mediterranean). Species richness peaked at the temperate latitudes of the study.

Further refined analyses of the data included the evaluation of the effects of additional field management factors and environmental effects (climate conditions and soil properties) on earthworm community metrics. Here the statistically significant effects are reported. There was no statistically significant evidence for the effects of the remaining explanatory variables when modeled either alone or combined with other explanatory variables.

TABLE 5.1

EFFECT	DENSITY		FRESH MASS		NUMBER OF SPECIES	
	F	<i>p</i>	F	<i>p</i>	F	<i>p</i>
Region	13.75	<0.0001	6.52	<0.0001	29.04	<0.0001
Management	0.58	0.449	0.00	0.988	1.20	0.276
Region x Management	0.77	0.628	0.90	0.523	1.08	0.382

Table 5.1. Results of generalized linear mixed model (GLMM) analyses for earthworm total density, total fresh mass and number of species (richness) covering nine pedoclimatic regions in Europe. Management refers to the comparison between organic and conventional management. Statistically significant effects are highlighted in bold. (Source: SoildiverAgro Deliverable Report D3.3).

5.3.2 Effects of environmental factors

Temperature was the climatic factor with the strongest relationship with earthworm community metrics. Mean yearly temperature over the preceding 30-year period showed a negative relationship with earthworm total density ($p < 0.001$), total mass ($p = 0.002$) and richness ($p = 0.005$) (Fig. 5.1). These results are in agreement with the earlier reported geographical pattern of lowest earthworm abundances at the southernmost studied sites and highest values in the northernmost and coolest regions (deliverable report D3.3). There were no statistically discernible relationships between the precipitation variables and earthworm community metrics unlike what was reported by Phillips et al. (2019) in their global study. The temperature and soil moisture conditions are, however, closely interlinked and the negative effect of high temperature on earthworm abundance likely relates to the increasingly severe summer droughts at the mid and southern latitudes of the study.

Of the soil properties, a negative association of soil pH ($p = 0.023$) and bioavailable Fe ($p = 0.002$) with the proportion of anecic earthworms was also detected. Texture is one of the key inherent soil properties affecting earthworm abundance but in the present data no texture effect was found. A likely explanation for this was the relatively small variation in the soil texture across the studied sites, as all soils were loams of varying particle size compositions except for one field where soil was classified as clay.

Figure 5.1. Model predictions (mean with the 95% confidence limits) of the relationships between the mean annual temperature and (a) earthworm total density, (b) earthworm total mass and (c) number of earthworm species (n=188 fields).

5.3.3 Effects of management

None of the variables describing the agricultural management had statistically discernible effects on earthworm density, biomass or species richness. However, in both organic and conventional systems the proportion of endogeic earthworms in the community was higher when crop residues were incorporated in the soil ($p < 0.0001$; Fig 5.2). This is due to the decline of other ecological groups which rely more strongly on surface residues as a food source and as a protective layer.

Figure 5.2. Proportion of endogeic earthworms of the total population under two different residue treatments at each conventional and organic managements (means and their 95% confidence limits).

Furthermore, the proportion of juvenile earthworms was higher in organic management than in conventional management ($p=0.013$). Crop rotation systems also significantly differed from each other, with the highest juvenile proportions being found in short rotations ($p=0.046$) (Fig. 5.3).

The study fields were classified according to additional factors potentially affecting abundance and species composition of earthworm communities. For instance, of the variables accounted for, the tillage regime, organic manure application and inclusion of legumes in the crop rotations are all potential factors influencing earthworm numbers (Edwards & Arancon, 2022). It was therefore somewhat unexpected that it was not possible to detect any relationships with none of earthworm community metrics. It is possible that these analyses can still be improved, for instance, in the case of highly influential soil tillage (Briones & Schmidt, 2017; van Capelle et al., 2012) by using a more effective classification of tillage methods, although discerning the management effects in this type of non-experimental study would be difficult. With the widely varying management regimes, positive and negative factors can cancel each other's effects out lowering the chances of detecting the impact of individual/local factors.

Figure 5.3. Proportion of juvenile individuals of all individuals in conventional and organic management under three different crop rotation systems (means with 95% confidence limits).

The usage of pesticides in conventional management is a potential negative influence for earthworms (Pelosi et al., 2014). However, in field conditions the effects of these applications may be relatively small compared with more influential management measures and be masked by them. This seems plausible in cereal fields of the present study where mainly herbicides – with comparatively mild negative effects on earthworms – were used.

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6 Biodiversity analysis

6.1 Introduction

In the preceding chapters, the relationship of different organism groups with metadata comprising agricultural, climatological, soil physical and soil chemical data was investigated. In this chapter, biodiversity data of prokaryote, fungi and nematodes were joined together and linked with the same metadata in a multivariate statistical approach. Earthworms were excluded from this analysis because its data was generated in a complete other way (microscopic analysis with absolute numbers versus molecular data with relative amounts) or was missing for certain regions due to climatological conditions (no earthworms were found). As a consequence, the earthworm data would jeopardise the statistical analysis.

Integrating the diversity of various organism groups, such as bacteria, fungi, and nematodes, is the way to go for comprehensive biodiversity assessments. These organisms play fundamental roles in ecosystem functioning and services. Bacteria are pivotal in nutrient cycling, decomposing organic material, and influencing soil structure and fertility (Gans et al., 2005). Fungi, on the other hand, are essential for nutrient acquisition, particularly through mycorrhizal associations, which enhance plant nutrient uptake (Smith & Read, 2008). Nematodes contribute to the decomposition process by feeding on bacteria and fungi, thus regulating microbial populations and facilitating nutrient mineralization (Bongers & Ferris, 1999). By evaluating these diverse groups together, researchers can gain a holistic understanding of ecosystem health and resilience, as each group influences the others and collectively maintains ecosystem stability.

The inclusion of multiple organism groups in biodiversity assessments is also necessary to detect and understand complex ecological interactions and feedback mechanisms. For example, changes in bacterial communities can alter fungal population dynamics and vice versa, affecting overall soil health and plant growth (van der Heijden et al., 2008). Similarly, nematodes, by preying on microbes, can influence microbial community composition and activity, impacting soil nutrient cycles (Neher, 2010). Analyses based on one organism group has its advantages, not in the least as analysis methods are more simple and accessible for a broader range of researchers, but it can lead to incomplete assessments, overlooking critical interactions that underpin ecosystem processes. Therefore, incorporating the diversity of bacteria, fungi, and nematodes provides a more accurate and comprehensive picture of biodiversity and its functional implications, essential for informed conservation and management strategies (Wall et al., 2012).

6.2 Material and Methods

6.2.1 Construction of co-abundance networks

The relationship between OTUs (including ASVs) was described using co-abundance networks. To avoid rare OTUs having a too large influence on the statistical results, the data was pre-filtered by abundance. Namely, only OTUs with a relative abundance of at least 0.03% for prokaryotes, 0.2% for eukaryotes (fungal species) and 0.5% per nematodes was considered in the analysis. Then, only OTUs present on each sample were included in the analysis. The relative abundance threshold were selected to keep approximately 80% of the average relative abundance. These values are relatively high because further steps down the pipeline (clustering, sPLS, bipartite network) introduce further filters, so it is desirable not to filter out rare OTUs that may have a key ecosystem function.

Co-abundance networks were built using the SPIEC-EASI pipeline (Kurtz et al., 2015) through the implementation included in the SpiecEasi package (version 1.1.3). This algorithm was selected, as it is based on conditional independence, so it is generally more robust against spurious associations than traditional methods based on correlations.

The models were fitted using the `multi.spiec.easi` function, which enables combining multiple compositional datasets. Hence, the non-normalized OUT tables for bacteria, fungi and nematodes were passed as inputs. The model was fitted by covariance selection with LASSO regularization (Kurtz et al., 2015). Model selection was done by `pulsar` with 20 random subsamples.

The results of the SPIEC-EASI pipeline were represented as a graph, where the vertices are the OTUs measured. The edges describe the relationships between OTUs, with a positive value indicates a positive association (e.g., synergism) and a negative one the opposite (e.g., competition). Edges were calculated from the optimal covariance matrix of the fitted model and converted to correlations to facilitate interpretation.

6.2.2 Clustering of highly related OTUs

Clusters of highly related OTUs were identified using the spin-glass community detection algorithm (Reichardt & Bornholdt, 2006) from the co-abundance networks estimated using SPIEC-EASI with default arguments. This results in the detection of highly connected groups of OTUs (including bacteria, fungi and nematodes).

For further analysis, the results of the clustering were combined with the raw copies measured for each OTUs. Hence, the total copies of bacterial, fungal and nematode OTUs for each cluster on each sample were calculated.

6.2.3 Relationships between biodiversity, soil characteristic, climate conditions and agricultural management

Biodiversity was related to meta-information on soil characteristics by sparse Partial Least Squares (sPLS) (Lê Cao et al., 2008) using the functions included in the mixOmics package (version 6.23.4). PLS are a type of dimensionality reduction technique, where the data from two separate matrix are projected (in a latent space) in a manner that optimizes their covariance. In this sense, it can be seen as an extension of Principal Component Analysis (PCA) to separate datasets. The sPLS algorithm combines PLS with LASSO regularization to reduce the number of variables included in the model.

The X matrix for the sPLS comprises the soil characteristics, climate conditions and agricultural management variables (see D3.2 and table A1.A till A1.3). Then, the Y matrix includes the raw copies OTUs per cluster (independently for bacteria, fungi and nematodes) observed. The model was defined as a canonical problem (as opposed to regression), as there is no clear cause-effect between X and Y. Hyperparameter tuning was done by M-fold cross-validation with 10 folds, up to 8 components and 2 independent repeats.

The key associations within the sPLS models were identified using relevance association networks (González et al., 2012) using the implementation included in mixOmics. Cut-off values were defined independently for each region to identify the most relevant interactions.

6.3 Results

6.3.1 Co-abundance networks

Figure 6.1 illustrates the co-abundance networks relating bacteria, fungi and nematodes for each of the 9 regions studied. In general, the networks are highly connected, hinting at the possibility of complex interactions between OTUs. Therefore, complex network analysis methods (beyond descriptive indexes) are required to describe these relations. Figure 6.2 illustrates the degree distribution of the co-abundance networks. The figure shows clear similarities between the nine graphs. This could indicate the existence of a similar structural arrangement between the different regions. The weights of the co-abundance network indicates the type of relation between OTUs, with positive values showing positive (e.g., synergism) associations and negative ones the opposite (e.g., competition). Figure 6.3 depicts the distribution of the edge weights among the 9 different regions studied. In every case, the distribution is by modal, with two modes clearly separated above and below $w = 0$. Furthermore, positive weights are more common than negative ones, potentially indicating that synergistic relations are more common than competition (or easier to estimate from ad-hoc data). The range of the weights distribution is similar between areas (except for the Atlantic

Central area), further supporting the previous conclusion that there might be similar structural arrangements in the soil ecosystem of the 9 areas.

Figure 6.1. Co-abundance networks estimated by the SPIEC-EASI algorithm for each of the pedoclimatic regions.

Figure 6.2. Degree rank plot for the co-abundance networks estimated by the SPIEC-EASI algorithm for each of the pedoclimatic regions (colours).

Figure 6.3. Distribution of the association between OTUs (estimated as the weight of the graph estimated by SPIEC-EASI) for each region. Positive values indicate positive associations (e.g., synergism), whereas negative ones the opposite (e.g., competition).

6.3.2 Communities of highly related OTUs

To reduce the dimensionality of the biodiversity data, the OTUs were grouped in highly-connected communities. Clusters include a combination of bacterial, fungal and nematode OTUs. As shown in Tables 6.1 till 6.3, the number of OTUs included on each cluster varies largely among regions. The largest clusters include approximately 400 bacterial OTUs, 40 fungal OTUs and 16 nematode OTUs; whereas the smallest clusters include less than 5 OTUs. The difference in magnitude in the number of bacterial, fungal and nematode OTUs is due to the difference of magnitude in the original data (there are 10 times more bacteria than fungi in the 16S).

Figure 6.4 illustrates the contribution of each cluster to the relative abundance of bacteria, fungi or nematodes on each sampling location. This plot illustrates that there is a clear variation between sites, with some clusters being more prevalent in some areas than others. This is of high interest, especially considering that there are relatively large differences in the total number of OTUs included on each cluster (Tables 6.1 till 6.3). Moreover, there are also clear differences among groups (bacteria/fungi/nematode), with some clusters being relevant only for some. This may indicate

specialization between clusters, which could potentially be related to soil characteristics, environmental conditions or management practices.

TABLE 6.1

CLUS- TER	ATL_ CENT	ATL_ NORTH	BOR	CONT	LUSIT	MED_ NORTH	MED_ SOUTH	NEM	PANN
1	352	411	219	253	264	332	29	279	215
2	386	3	358	43	0	314	280	181	5
3	77	205	8	179	3	71	217	147	7
4	119	21	169	56	67	48	40	157	2
5	113	108	78	139	113	9	7	235	219
6	0	131	6	3	69	5	98	8	5
7	65	54	11	2	100	34	16	2	19
8	12	9	112	7	193	14	61	9	25
9	0	1	14	57	45	6	50	1	26
10	0	6	3	16	1	1	41	25	90
11	0	12	26	5	6	42	6	2	21
12	0	6	19	7	83	8	4	34	3
13	0	16	17	19	37	2	24	13	11
14	0	18	15	4	1	17	20	2	2
15	0	2	2	77	8	8	0	8	3
16	0	13	5	19	2	2	3	2	49
17	0	5	6	7	3	2	1	1	4
18	0	3	3	6	13	5	12	3	5
19	0	1	4	16	5	1	3	2	19
20	0	2	3	16	4	5	5	2	2
21	0	10	2	3	2	1	2	1	3
22	0	3	5	2	8	1	3	1	1
23	0	1	6	2	4	1	0	0	5
24	0	2	0	5	7	0	1	0	1
25	0	1	0	1	5	0	1	0	0

Table 6.1. Number of bacterial OTUs included on each cluster for each region. Atl_cent = Atlantic Central, Atl_north = Atlantic North, Bor = Boreal, Cont = Continental, Lusit = Lusitanian, Med_north = Mediterranean North, Med_south = Mediterranean South, Nem = Nemoral, Pann = Pannonian.

TABLE 6.2

CLUS- TER	ATL_ CENT	ATL_ NORTH	BOR	CONT	LUSIT	MED_ NORTH	MED_ SOUTH	NEM	PANN
1	38	30	8	34	24	32	3	19	33
2	34	1	15	3	1	34	25	13	5
3	11	9	1	23	1	14	24	37	4
4	8	6	28	1	11	13	12	7	7
5	20	21	12	8	12	5	5	25	22
6	1	6	3	3	5	5	11	2	11
7	5	2	6	1	3	11	6	3	5
8	0	1	14	10	41	5	8	1	8
9	0	2	4	4	7	3	6	2	2
10	0	3	2	7	1	3	10	1	3
11	0	3	4	6	1	0	2	1	5
12	0	0	1	6	0	0	1	0	4
13	0	1	0	1	4	1	0	0	15
14	0	0	1	1	1	1	1	0	11
15	0	0	1	2	0	0	1	1	1
16	0	2	1	0	0	0	3	0	0
17	0	0	0	3	1	0	0	0	1
18	0	1	0	2	1	0	0	1	1
19	0	1	0	0	1	0	0	1	3
20	0	0	0	0	0	0	1	0	2
21	0	0	0	0	1	0	0	1	0
22	0	0	0	1	0	0	0	0	0
23	0	0	1	1	0	0	1	0	0

Table 6.2. Number of fungal OTUs included on each cluster for each region. Atl_cent = Atlantic Central, Atl_north = Atlantic North, Bor = Boreal, Cont = Continental, Lusit = Lusitanian, Med_north = Mediterranean North, Med_south = Mediterranean South, Nem = Nemoral, Pann = Pannonian.

TABLE 6.3

CLUS- TER	ATL_ CENT	ATL_ NORTH	BOR	CONT	LUSIT	MED_ NORTH	MED_ SOUTH	NEM	PANN
1	12	16	2	12	5	13	1	5	18
2	9	1	14	1	2	10	10	4	1
3	11	6	0	7	5	9	10	27	1
4	3	0	11	0	5	5	4	7	0
5	21	11	3	6	4	1	2	19	11
6	0	4	2	1	1	1	6	1	7
7	9	3	0	2	1	2	2	1	3
8	0	2	5	1	9	2	2	1	8
9	1	1	2	2	0	1	2	1	0
10	0	0	0	3	0	0	0	0	2
11	0	3	0	2	3	3	0	1	0
12	0	0	0	3	0	0	1	0	1
13	0	0	1	3	2	1	0	0	3
14	0	2	1	0	0	0	0	0	3
15	0	0	2	4	2	0	0	0	3
16	0	2	1	1	0	1	0	2	0
17	0	1	0	0	2	0	0	0	0
18	0	1	1	4	0	0	1	1	4
19	0	5	0	1	1	3	0	3	2
20	0	1	4	1	0	0	2	1	1
21	0	1	0	0	0	0	0	1	2
22	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	1	0
23	0	0	1	3	0	2	0	1	4
24	0	1	1	0	0	0	0	0	1

Table 6.3. Number of nematode OTUs included on each cluster for each region. Atl_cent = Atlantic Central, Atl_north = Atlantic North, Bor = Boreal, Cont = Continental, Lusit = Lusitanian, Med_north = Mediterranean North, Med_south = Mediterranean South, Nem = Nemoral, Pann = Pannonian.

Figure 6.4. Contribution of each cluster to the relative abundance of bacterial, fungal or nematode OTUs for each of the sampling sites. The data is grouped in facets according to the regions.

6.3.3 Key relationships between biodiversity, soil characteristic, climate conditions and agricultural management

An sPLS model was fitted to relate the metadata of the sampling sites (soil characteristics, climate conditions and agricultural management) with biodiversity (represented by the clusters from section 6.3.2). An sPLS model with eight components was fitted to each pedoclimatic area. Table 6.4 reports the proportion of the variance of each block (block X being the metadata and block Y the biodiversity) described by each subsequent component. These values illustrate the complexity of the dataset and the interactions between both components. The first two components never describe even a half of the total variance of either block. This justifies the need for a high-dimensional sPLS model.

On average, the sPLS models with eight components describe roughly an 80% of the variance in the metadata block and a 70% of the variance in the biodiversity block. This difference in proportions might be due to the biodiversity block being more complex than the other one. It is also worth noting that the Atlantic Central is the only pedoclimatic area where sPLS model describes a higher proportion of the variance in the biodiversity dataset than on the metadata one.

Although the sPLS model includes variable selection, the fitted model still includes a large number of complex interactions, making it impossible to identify the key associations between metadata variables and biodiversity. Hence, a relevance association networks were performed for each area to identify the key associations for each pedoclimatic area. The results are illustrated in Figures 6.5 till 6.13.

TABLE 6.4

REGION	BLOCK	COM							
		p.1	p.2	P.3	p.4	p.5	p.6	p.7	p.8
Atl_C	Metadata	0.39	0.48	0.56	0.64	0.70	0.74	0.79	0.84
	Biodiv.	0.12	0.22	0.31	0.49	0.44	0.52	0.57	0.64
Atl_N	Metadata	0.20	0.34	0.52	0.38	0.64	0.68	0.72	0.75
	Biodiv.	0.21	0.38	0.50	0.59	0.66	0.72	0.79	0.82
Bor	Metadata	0.25	0.38	0.51	0.64	0.71	0.75	0.81	0.85
	Biodiv.	0.09	0.22	0.33	0.41	0.48	0.56	0.62	0.69
Cont	Metadata	0.19	0.33	0.49	0.67	0.72	0.75	0.81	0.84
	Biodiv.	0.11	0.21	0.30	0.37	0.46	0.53	0.58	0.65
Lusit	Metadata	0.29	0.43	0.56	0.64	0.70	0.76	0.80	0.84
	Biodiv.	0.12	0.27	0.38	0.49	0.57	0.64	0.68	0.72
Med_N	Metadata	0.29	0.46	0.60	0.67	0.73	0.79	0.84	0.87
	Biodiv.	0.14	0.25	0.33	0.41	0.48	0.55	0.62	0.67
Med_S	Metadata	0.27	0.39	0.50	0.58	0.65	0.72	0.76	0.79
	Biodiv.	0.14	0.24	0.33	0.42	0.49	0.55	0.62	0.69
Nem	Metadata	0.28	0.45	0.53	0.66	0.72	0.79	0.82	0.85
	Biodiv.	0.16	0.24	0.33	0.39	0.49	0.46	0.62	0.67
Pann	Metadata	0.17	0.33	0.48	0.63	0.73	0.79	0.82	0.86
	Biodiv.	0.12	0.24	0.35	0.41	0.48	0.55	0.62	0.68

Table 6.4. Cumulative proportion variance of the two blocks (soil metadata and soil biodiversity) explained by the 8 components of the sPLS model fitted. Atl_C = Atlantic Central, Atl_N = Atlantic North, Bor = Boreal, Cont = Continental, Lusit = Lusitanian, Med_N = Mediterranean North, Med_S = Mediterranean South, Nem = Nemoral, Pann = Pannonian. Biodiv. = Biodiversity

There is large diversity in the associations identified as most relevant between areas, both in terms of the metadata variables and the kingdom of the biodiversity. Nonetheless, there are some similarities. Variables related to the pH are identified as relevant for the Atlantic Central (associated with bacteria from Cluster #2), Boreal (bacteria from Cluster #8) and the Pannonian regions (nematodes and fungi from Cluster #5). Different form of total C are also key variables for the Continental (bacteria from Cluster #4), Boreal (nematodes from cluster #24, fungi from cluster #5 and bacteria from cluster #21), Lusitanian (bacteria and fungi from cluster #8), Mediterranean South (fungi from cluster #3), Nemoral (fungi from cluster #3 and bacteria from cluster #2) and Pannonian (nematodes from cluster #24) regions. Other variables related to the chemical composition of the soil are also identified as key, such as those related to the nitrogen content, CaCO₃, SO₄, Mn, Zn and NO₃.

Environmental variables (related to temperature or precipitation) are also identified as strongly associated with biodiversity in the Continental (fungi from cluster #4), Atlantic North (bacteria from cluster #4), Mediterranean North (fungi from cluster #14), Mediterranean South (bacteria and fungi from cluster #3) and Pannonian (bacteria from cluster #11) regions. Variables related to soil physical properties are sparingly identified as key, such as those related to the silt (Atlantic Central region), the sand content (Lusitanian region) or the aggregates size distribution (Lusitanian and Atlantic North regions).

The management practices is also identified as a key variable in several regions. Namely, in the Atlantic North (related to bacteria from cluster #5), Mediterranean North (to bacteria from cluster #2), Mediterranean South (to bacteria and to fungi from cluster #3). Furthermore, the total glyphosate compounds in the soil are identified as key in the Mediterranean South (to bacteria from cluster #13).

Figure 6.5. Relevance association network from the sPLS model fitted to the data obtained from samples from the Continental pedoclimatic area.

Figure 6.6. Relevance association network from the sPLS model fitted to the data obtained from samples from the Atlantic Central pedoclimatic area.

Figure 6.7. Relevance association network from the sPLS model fitted to the data obtained from samples from the Atlantic North pedoclimatic area.

Figure 6.8. Relevance association network from the sPLS model fitted to the data obtained from samples from the Boreal pedoclimatic area.

Figure 6.9. Relevance association network from the sPLS model fitted to the data obtained from samples from the Lusitanian pedoclimatic area.

Figure 6.10. Relevance association network from the sPLS model fitted to the data obtained from samples from the Mediterranean North pedoclimatic area.

Figure 6.11. Relevance association network from the sPLS model fitted to the data obtained from samples from the Mediterranean South pedoclimatic area.

Figure 6.12. Relevance association network from the sPLS model fitted to the data obtained from samples from the Nemoral pedoclimatic area.

Figure 6.13. Relevance association network from the sPLS model fitted to the data obtained from samples from the Pannonian pedoclimatic area.

6.4 References

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ANNEXES-tables

TABLE A1.1

SAMPLE ID	LATI-TUDE	LONGI-TUDE	REGION	LANDFORM	AGRI	#Y	TEXTURE
ACO1A	50,7521820	3,2980160	Atl_cent	Plain	Org	6	silt loam
ACO1B	50,7455600	3,2652310	Atl_cent	Plain	Org	19	silt loam
ACO1C	50,7432950	3,2650900	Atl_cent	Plain	Org	1	silt loam
ACO2A	50,7697300	3,7794500	Atl_cent	Plain	Org	9	silt loam
ACO3A	50,9272200	3,4308130	Atl_cent	Plain	Org	5	sandy loam
ACO4A	51,1091600	4,8497100	Atl_cent	Plain	Org	25	sandy loam
ACO4B	51,1205500	4,8733300	Atl_cent	Plain	Org	10	sandy loam
ACO4C	51,0977700	4,8219300	Atl_cent	Plain	Org	4	sandy loam
ACO5A	51,1414000	4,8299400	Atl_cent	Plain	Org	11	sandy loam
ACO5B	51,1402800	4,8322000	Atl_cent	Plain	Org	11	sandy loam
ACO6A	51,2680800	4,1831300	Atl_cent	Plain	Org	25	sandy loam
ACO6B	51,2791400	4,1958330	Atl_cent	Plain	Org	6	loam
ACC1A	50,7533330	3,3002780	Atl_cent	Plain	Conv	>20	silt loam
ACC2A	50,7583330	3,3716670	Atl_cent	Plain	Conv	>20	silt loam
ACC3A	50,8519440	3,7066670	Atl_cent	Plain	Conv	>20	silt loam
ACC4A	50,9247220	3,4352780	Atl_cent	Plain	Conv	>20	sandy loam
ACC5A	50,7375000	3,2722220	Atl_cent	Plain	Conv	>20	silt loam
ACC6A	51,0502780	4,7925000	Atl_cent	Plain	Conv	>20	sandy loam
ACC6B	51,0494440	4,7908330	Atl_cent	Plain	Conv	>20	sandy loam
ACC7A	51,0569440	4,2966670	Atl_cent	Plain	Conv	>20	sandy loam
ACC8A	51,0213890	4,3744440	Atl_cent	Plain	Conv	>20	sandy loam
ACC8B	50,9618900	4,3789900	Atl_cent	Plain	Conv	>20	silt loam
ACC9A	51,0961110	4,7925000	Atl_cent	Plain	Conv	>20	sandy loam
ACC10A	51,2691670	4,1852780	Atl_cent	Plain	Conv	>20	sandy loam
ACC11A	51,2805560	4,1966670	Atl_cent	Plain	Conv	>20	sandy loam
ANC1A	55,8788889	10,1608333	Atl_cent	Plain	Conv	>10	sandy loam
ANC1B	55,8819444	10,1600000	Atl_north	Plain	Conv	>10	sandy loam
ANC2A	55,3138889	9,3127778	Atl_north	Plain	Conv	>10	sandy loam
ANC2B	55,3166667	9,3094444	Atl_north	Plain	Conv	>10	sandy loam
ANC3A	55,6088889	9,3841667	Atl_north	Plain	Conv	>10	sandy loam
ANC3B	55,6088889	9,3883333	Atl_north	Plain	Conv	>10	sandy loam

ANC4A	55,7766667	9,3819444	Atl_north	Plain	Conv	>10	sandy loam
ANC4B	55,7794444	9,3827778	Atl_north	Plain	Conv	>10	sandy loam
ANC5A	55,2830556	9,3794444	Atl_north	Plain	Conv	>10	sandy loam
ANC5B	55,2816667	9,3847222	Atl_north	Plain	Conv	>10	sandy loam
ANO1A	55,8763889	10,1650000	Atl_north	Plain	Org	>10	sandy loam
ANO1B	55,8766667	10,1675000	Atl_north	Plain	Org	>10	sandy loam
ANO2A	55,3138889	9,3127778	Atl_north	Plain	Org	>10	sandy loam
ANO2B	55,3166667	9,3094444	Atl_north	Plain	Org	>10	sandy loam
ANO3A	55,6111111	9,3769444	Atl_north	Plain	Org	>10	sandy loam
ANO3B	55,6136111	9,3713889	Atl_north	Plain	Org	>10	sandy loam
ANO4A	55,5666667	9,3163889	Atl_north	Plain	Org	>10	sandy loam
ANO4B	55,5722222	9,3166667	Atl_north	Plain	Org	>10	sandy loam
ANO5A	55,2769444	9,3744444	Atl_north	Plain	Org	>10	sandy loam
ANO5B	55,2750000	9,3750000	Atl_north	Plain	Org	>10	sandy loam
BORO1A	60,6548396	25,8135300	Boreal	Hill	Org	26	silt loam
BORO1B	60,6562243	25,8106727	Boreal	Hill	Org	26	loam
BORC1A	60,6928686	25,7765581	Boreal	Plain	Conv	60	sandy loam
BORC1B	60,6865124	25,8247286	Boreal	Piedmont or fan	Conv	60	sandy clay loam
BORO2A	60,6330319	22,7878863	Boreal	Plain	Org	25	loam
BORO2B	60,6336644	22,7902153	Boreal	Plain	Org	25	loam
BORC2A	60,6345088	22,7987537	Boreal	Plain	Conv	60	loam
BORC2B	60,6311410	22,7963225	Boreal	Plain	Conv	60	loam
BORO3A	61,8347918	27,7784090	Boreal	Piedmont or fan	Org	24	sandy loam
BORO3B	61,8354354	27,7775674	Boreal	Piedmont or fan	Org	24	sandy loam
BORC3A	61,8722711	27,7168872	Boreal	Plain	Conv	60	sandy loam
BORC3B	61,8747538	27,7128158	Boreal	Plain	Conv	60	sandy loam
BORO4A	61,7122906	23,1557952	Boreal	Plain	Org	23	silt loam
BORO4B	61,7115371	23,1584459	Boreal	Piedmont or fan	Org	23	silt loam
BORC4A	61,6217431	23,1417679	Boreal	Plain	Conv	60	silt loam
BORC4B	61,6243353	23,1658098	Boreal	Hill	Conv	25	silt loam
BORO5A	60,2840180	22,5696985	Boreal	Plain	Org	5	sandy clay loam
BORO5B	60,2823531	22,5727065	Boreal	Plain	Org	5	loam
BORC5A	60,2794352	22,5745669	Boreal	Piedmont or fan	Conv	15	sandy clay loam
BORC5B	60,2784542	22,5752542	Boreal	Piedmont or fan	Conv	15	loam
CONC1A	52,1199160	11,5241150	Cont	Plain	Conv	>20	silt loam

CONC1B	52,1225510	11,5187700	Cont	Plain	Conv	>20	silt loam
CONC1C	52,1279020	11,5103030	Cont	Plain	Conv	>20	silt loam
CONC2A	52,2149010	11,2975440	Cont	Plain	Conv	>20	silt loam
CONC2B	52,2171890	11,2992750	Cont	Plain	Conv	>20	loam
CONC2C	52,2113710	11,3045170	Cont	Plain	Conv	>20	loam
CONC3A	52,0728750	11,5999070	Cont	Plain	Conv	>20	silt loam
CONC3B	52,0717120	11,6027330	Cont	Plain	Conv	>20	silt loam
CONC3C	52,0352690	11,5785130	Cont	Plain	Conv	>20	silt loam
CONC4A	52,0171110	11,3519120	Cont	Plain	Conv	>20	silt loam
CONO1A	52,9723650	11,5298430	Cont	Plain	Org	>10	silt loam
CONO1B	52,9704290	11,5292530	Cont	Plain	Org	>10	silt loam
CONO1C	52,9708820	11,5434900	Cont	Plain	Org	>10	silt loam
CONO2A	52,1162140	11,4720690	Cont	Plain	Org	>10	silt loam
CONO2B	52,1129660	11,4736710	Cont	Plain	Org	>10	silt loam
CONO2C	52,1215340	11,4620000	Cont	Plain	Org	>10	silt loam
CONO3A	52,0616860	11,4960660	Cont	Plain	Org	>10	silt loam
CONO4A	52,6957910	11,2204020	Cont	Plain	Org	>10	loam
CONO4B	52,6870410	11,0631830	Cont	Plain	Org	>10	sandy loam
CONO4C	52,6841990	11,0704120	Cont	Plain	Org	>10	loam
LUSC1A	42,046306	-7,671583	Lusit	Plain	Conv	>20	sandy loam
LUSC1B	42,039806	-7,672750	Lusit	Plain	Conv	>20	sandy loam
LUSC2A	42,038583	-7,684114	Lusit	Plain	Conv	>30	sandy loam
LUSC2B	42,017464	-7,6940000	Lusit	Plain	Conv	>30	sandy loam
LUSC3A	42,075250	-7,6501972	Lusit	Plain	Conv	>30	sandy loam
LUSC3B	42,073417	-7,6386111	Lusit	Plain	Conv	>30	sandy loam
LUSC4A	42,053361	-7,7313333	Lusit	Plain	Conv	>30	sandy loam
LUSC4B	42,080111	-7,6561111	Lusit	Plain	Conv	>30	sandy loam
LUSC5A	42,162972	-7,7163056	Lusit	Plain	Conv	15	loam
LUSC5B	42,026722	-7,7716667	Lusit	Plain	Conv	>30	sandy loam
LUSO1A	43,306806	-8,1229444	Lusit	Plain	Org	2	silt loam
LUSO1B	43,306806	-8,1229722	Lusit	Piedmont or fan	Org	6	sandy loam
LUSO2A	42,373361	-7,9861944	Lusit	Plateau or upper terrace	Org	5	sandy loam
LUSO2B	42,369750	-7,9813889	Lusit	Plateau or upper terrace	Org	5	sandy loam
LUSO3A	42,900972	-7,2480833	Lusit	Plain	Org	14	silt loam
LUSO3B	42,825833	-7,9108889	Lusit	Plain	Org	10	sandy loam
LUSO4A	43,523222	-7,4066667	Lusit	Piedmont or fan	Org	3	sandy loam

LUSO4B	43,530306	-7,4061667	Lusit	Piedmont or fan	Org	3	sandy loam
LUSO4C	43,530306	-7,4019444	Lusit	Piedmont or fan	Org	3	sandy loam
LUSO5A	43,094222	-8,0586389	Lusit	Piedmont or fan	Org	13	loam
LUSO5B	43,090778	-8,0596667	Lusit	Piedmont or fan	Org	13	loam
LUSO6A	42,067778	-7,7554444	Lusit	Plain	Org	10	sandy loam
LUSO6B	42,069583	-7,7528611	Lusit	Plain	Org	10	sandy loam
MNO1A	37,8692300	-2,3620510	Med_north	Plain	Org	12	sandy loam
MNO1B	37,8695740	-2,3616210	Med_north	Plain	Org	12	sandy loam
MNO2A	37,9218340	-2,0541170	Med_north	Plain	Org	10	sandy loam
MNO2B	37,9229000	-2,0536850	Med_north	Plain	Org	10	loam
MNO3A	37,9261680	-2,1756200	Med_north	Plain	Org	13	sandy loam
MNO3B	37,9263120	-2,1759070	Med_north	Plain	Org	13	sandy loam
MNO4A	37,8530700	-2,0012670	Med_north	Plateau or upper terrace	Org	9	loam
MNO4B	37,8523720	-2,0013450	Med_north	Plateau or upper terrace	Org	9	loam
MNO5A	37,9272690	-2,0816970	Med_north	Plain	Org	11	loam
MNO5B	37,9269580	-2,0810610	Med_north	Plain	Org	11	sandy loam
MNC1A	39,1556690	-1,8703530	Med_north	Plain	Conv	20	sandy loam
MNC1B	39,1590090	-1,8704120	Med_north	Plain	Conv	20	sandy loam
MNC2A	37,9291730	-2,0638020	Med_north	Plain	Conv	27	sandy loam
MNC2B	37,9287380	-2,0667260	Med_north	Plain	Conv	27	sandy loam
MNC3A	39,1583640	-1,8480730	Med_north	Plain	Conv	20	sandy loam
MNC3B	39,1566530	-1,8476170	Med_north	Plain	Conv	20	sandy loam
MNC4A	39,6561491	-1,4607592	Med_north	Plain	Conv	>20	sandy loam
MNC4B	39,6525690	-1,4566560	Med_north	Plain	Conv	>20	sandy loam
MNC5A	39,7463680	-1,2136890	Med_north	Plain	Conv	30	sandy loam
MNC5B	39,7456870	-1,2166010	Med_north	Plain	Conv	30	sandy loam
MSO1A	37,9263400	-1,7776900	Med_south	Plain	Org	19	loam
MSO1B	37,9269400	-1,7782040	Med_south	Plain	Org	19	loam
MSO2A	37,8211540	-1,8429010	Med_south	Plain	Org	10	sandy loam
MSO2B	37,9400190	-1,8260390	Med_south	Plain	Org	10	sandy loam
MSO3A	37,8269210	-1,8196250	Med_south	Plain	Org	5	sandy loam
MSO3B	37,8293100	-1,8369870	Med_south	Plain	Org	5	loam
MSO4A	37,7953830	-1,9176540	Med_south	Plain	Org	6	loam
MSO4B	37,7977600	-1,9221650	Med_south	Plain	Org	6	loam
MSO5A	37,6790650	-1,4042890	Med_south	Plain	Org	3	silt loam

MSO5B	37,6770360	-1,3980880	Med_south	Plain	Org	3	loam
MSC1A	37,8024720	-1,0524440	Med_south	Plain	Conv	4	sandy clay loam
MSC1B	37,8031290	-1,0530440	Med_south	Plain	Conv	4	loam
MSC2A	37,7714500	-1,0389400	Med_south	Plain	Conv	25	loam
MSC2B	37,7682365	-1,0368050	Med_south	Plain	Conv	25	sandy loam
MSC3A	37,8211540	-1,0429010	Med_south	Plain	Conv	> 40	loam
MSC3B	37,8225020	-1,0427040	Med_south	Plain	Conv	> 40	sandy loam
MSC4A	37,8047170	-1,0558790	Med_south	Plain	Conv	> 40	loam
MSC4B	37,8050070	-1,0563400	Med_south	Plain	Conv	> 40	loam
MSC5A	37,7909910	-1,0528830	Med_south	Plain	Conv	> 40	loam
MSC5B	37,7899050	-1,0533800	Med_south	Plain	Conv	> 40	loam
NEMO1A	58,4156180	26,9251410	Nemoral	Plain	Org	10	loam
NEMO1B	58,4137920	26,9325110	Nemoral	Plain	Org	10	loam
NEMO2A	58,4478940	26,8148210	Nemoral	Plain	Org	10	sandy loam
NEMO2B	58,4470900	26,8115760	Nemoral	Plain	Org	10	sandy loam
NEMO3A	58,2455420	25,9240720	Nemoral	Plain	Org	18	sandy loam
NEMO3B	58,2448060	25,9200420	Nemoral	Plain	Org	18	loam
NEMO4A	57,8918420	24,3990000	Nemoral	Plain	Org	10	sandy loam
NEMO4B	57,8918460	24,4033360	Nemoral	Plain	Org	10	sandy loam
NEMO5A	58,4400510	24,0145600	Nemoral	Plain	Org	10	sandy loam
NEMO5B	58,4406970	24,0123930	Nemoral	Plain	Org	10	sandy loam
NEMC1A	59,2433000	26,4486000	Nemoral	Plain	Conv	20	loam
NEMC1B	59,2426250	26,4453440	Nemoral	Plain	Conv	20	loam
NEMC2A	58,1181090	25,2346790	Nemoral	Plain	Conv	20	sandy loam
NEMC2B	58,1212470	25,2358270	Nemoral	Plain	Conv	20	sandy loam
NEMC3A	58,6562450	24,9520930	Nemoral	Plain	Conv	15	sandy loam
NEMC3B	58,6552990	24,9448010	Nemoral	Plain	Conv	15	sandy loam
NEMC4A	58,2460830	26,4920740	Nemoral	Plain	Conv	-	sandy loam
NEMC4B	58,2498430	26,4925680	Nemoral	Plain	Conv	-	sandy loam
NEMC5A	57,8713370	26,0735840	Nemoral	Plain	Conv	20	sandy loam
NEMC5B	57,8711600	26,0841050	Nemoral	Plain	Conv	20	loam
PANC1A	45,0208333	20,5091670	Pann	Plain	Conv	>20	clay
PANC1B	45,0272222	20,5008330	Pann	Plain	Conv	>20	silt loam
PANC2A	46,4753306	18,2725306	Pann	Hill	Conv	>20	loam
PANC2B	46,4663861	18,2885861	Pann	Hill	Conv	>20	loam
PANC3A	46,5833333	18,4186000	Pann	Hill	Conv	>20	loam
PANC3B	46,6789639	18,4205222	Pann	Hill	Conv	>20	loam
PANC4A	47,1406917	19,9585083	Pann	Plain	Conv	>10	loam
PANC4B	47,1379667	19,9519278	Pann	Plain	Conv	>10	silt loam

PANC5A	47,1370139	19,9521417	Pann	Plain	Conv	>10	loam
PANC5B	47,1330472	19,9580550	Pann	Plain	Conv	>10	loam
PANO1A	45,4544444	19,4627778	Pann	Plain	Org	6	sandy clay loam
PANO1B	45,4897222	19,4452778	Pann	Plain	Org	6	loam
PANO2A	46,5654444	17,6898972	Pann	Hill	Org	25	silt loam
PANO2B	46,5655833	17,7028861	Pann	Hill	Org	20	silt loam
PANO3A	46,5260778	18,3840250	Pann	Plain	Org	5	silt loam
PANO3B	46,5303611	18,3841278	Pann	Plain	Org	3	silt loam
PANO4A	47,5933944	20,8331220	Pann	Plain	Org	5	sandy loam
PANO4B	47,5429472	20,7730306	Pann	Plain	Org	5	sandy loam
PANO5A	47,5384528	20,7730194	Pann	Plain	Org	11	sandy loam
PANO5B	47,5183167	20,7638695	Pann	Plain	Org	5	sandy loam

Table A1.1. Metadata file 1, geographical data. Atl_cent = Atlantic Central, Atl_north = Atlantic North, Boreal = Boreal, Cont = Continental, Lusit = Lusitanian, Med_north = Mediterranean North, Med_south = Mediterranean South, Nemoral = Nemoral, Pann = Pannonian; landform: plain = <1% slope, piedmont or fan = 1-5% slope, plateau or upper terrace = 1-10% slope at >500m elevation, hill = 8-25% slope; Agri = agricultural management regime: org = organic farming, conv = conventional farming; #Y = number of years of the farming system.

TABLE A1.2

SAMPLE ID	MEAN °C 30Y	MEAN P 30Y	MEAN °C 1Y (*)	TOTAL P 1Y (*)	MEAN MIN. °C 1Y (*)	MEAN MAX. °C 1Y (*)	#D <0°C 1Y (*)	#D >30°C 1Y (*)
ACO1A	11	840	12,33	518,7	7,67	15,75	30	10
ACO1B	11	824	12,33	518,7	7,67	15,75	30	10
ACO1C	11	824	12,33	518,7	7,67	15,75	30	10
ACO2A	11	841	11,39	693,2	7,67	15,75	30	10
ACO3A	11	820	12,33	518,7	7,67	15,75	30	10
ACO4A	11	835	11,8	585,6	7,67	15,75	30	10
ACO4B	11	835	11,8	585,6	7,67	15,75	30	10
ACO4C	11	835	11,8	585,6	7,67	15,75	30	10
ACO5A	11	849	11,8	585,6	7,67	15,75	30	10
ACO5B	11	849	11,8	585,6	7,67	15,75	30	10
ACO6A	11	869	11,8	585,6	7,67	15,75	30	10
ACO6B	11	869	11,8	585,6	7,67	15,75	30	10
ACC1A	11	840	12,33	518,7	7,67	15,75	30	10
ACC2A	11	840	12,33	518,7	7,67	15,75	30	10

ACC3A	11	818	11,39	693,2	7,67	15,75	30	10
ACC4A	11	820	12,33	518,7	7,67	15,75	30	10
ACC5A	11	824	12,33	518,7	7,67	15,75	30	10
ACC6A	11	829	11,8	585,6	7,67	15,75	30	10
ACC6B	11	829	11,8	585,6	7,67	15,75	30	10
ACC7A	11	834	11,8	585,6	7,67	15,75	30	10
ACC8A	11	801	11,8	585,6	7,67	15,75	30	10
ACC8B	11	812	11,8	585,6	7,67	15,75	30	10
ACC9A	11	829	11,8	585,6	7,67	15,75	30	10
ACC10A	11	869	11,8	585,6	7,67	15,75	30	10
ACC11A	11	869	11,8	585,6	7,67	15,75	30	10
ANC1A	8,7	759	8,5	664,4	3,9	14,1	70	1
ANC1B	8,7	759	8,5	664,5	3,9	14,1	70	1
ANC2A	8,7	759	9,7	706,1	5,2	13,8	67	3
ANC2B	8,7	759	9,7	706,1	5,2	13,8	67	3
ANC3A	8,7	759	9,4	830,1	4,4	13,7	82	3
ANC3B	8,7	759	9,4	830,1	4,4	13,7	82	3
ANC4A	8,7	759	9,4	830,1	4,4	13,7	82	3
ANC4B	8,7	759	9,4	830,1	4,4	13,7	82	3
ANC5A	8,7	759	9,7	706,1	5,2	13,8	67	3
ANC5B	8,7	759	9,7	706,1	5,2	13,8	67	3
ANO1A	8,7	759	8,5	664,4	3,9	14,1	70	1
ANO1B	8,7	759	8,5	664,5	3,9	14,1	70	1
ANO2A	8,7	759	9,7	706,1	5,2	13,8	67	3
ANO2B	8,7	759	9,7	706,1	5,2	13,8	67	3
ANO3A	8,7	759	9,4	830,1	4,4	13,7	82	3
ANO3B	8,7	759	9,4	830,1	4,4	13,7	82	3
ANO4A	8,7	759	9,8	711,7	5,3	13,7	64	3
ANO4B	8,7	759	9,8	711,7	5,3	13,7	64	3
ANO5A	8,7	759	9,7	706,1	5,2	13,8	67	3
ANO5B	8,7	759	9,7	706,1	5,2	13,8	67	3
BORO1A	5,3	619	6,3	528	2,1	10,3	95	0
BORO1B	5,3	619	6,3	528	2,1	10,3	95	0
BORC1A	5,3	619	6,3	528	2,1	10,3	95	0
BORC1B	5,3	619	6,3	528	2,1	10,3	95	0
BORO2A	5,5	589	6,5	540	2,1	10,5	89	0
BORO2B	5,5	589	6,5	540	2,1	10,5	89	0
BORC2A	5,5	589	6,5	540	2,1	10,5	89	0
BORC2B	5,5	589	6,5	540	2,1	10,5	89	0

BORO3A	3,9	574	4,8	528	0,9	8,6	116	0
BORO3B	3,9	574	4,8	528	0,9	8,6	116	0
BORC3A	3,9	574	4,8	528	0,9	8,6	116	0
BORC3B	3,9	574	4,8	528	0,9	8,6	116	0
BORO4A	4,8	617	5,7	576	1,6	9,8	104	0
BORO4B	4,8	617	5,7	576	1,6	9,8	104	0
BORC4A	4,8	617	5,7	576	1,6	9,8	104	0
BORC4B	4,8	617	5,7	576	1,6	9,8	104	0
BORO5A	6	649	7	632	2,6	11	75	0
BORO5B	6	649	7	632	2,6	11	75	0
BORC5A	6	649	7	632	2,6	11	75	0
BORC5B	6	649	7	632	2,6	11	75	0
CONC1A	10,04	514,87	11,52	418,8	6,71	16,3	-	-
CONC1B	10,04	514,87	11,52	418,8	6,71	16,3	-	-
CONC1C	10,04	514,87	11,52	418,8	6,71	16,3	-	-
CONC2A	10,04	514,87	11,52	418,8	6,71	16,3	-	-
CONC2B	10,04	514,87	11,52	418,8	6,71	16,3	-	-
CONC2C	10,04	514,87	11,52	418,8	6,71	16,3	-	-
CONC3A	10,04	514,87	11,52	418,8	6,71	16,3	-	-
CONC3B	10,04	514,87	11,52	418,8	6,71	16,3	-	-
CONC3C	10,04	514,87	11,52	418,8	6,71	16,3	-	-
CONC4A	10,04	514,87	11,52	418,8	6,71	16,3	-	-
CONO1A	10,04	514,87	11,52	418,8	6,71	16,3	-	-
CONO1B	10,04	514,87	11,52	418,8	6,71	16,3	-	-
CONO1C	10,04	514,87	11,52	418,8	6,71	16,3	-	-
CONO2A	10,04	514,87	11,52	418,8	6,71	16,3	-	-
CONO2B	10,04	514,87	11,52	418,8	6,71	16,3	-	-
CONO2C	10,04	514,87	11,52	418,8	6,71	16,3	-	-
CONO3A	10,04	514,87	11,52	418,8	6,71	16,3	-	-
CONO4A	9,7	536,2	10,83	419,8	5,05	16,8	-	-
CONO4B	9,7	536,2	10,83	419,8	5,05	16,8	-	-
CONO4C	9,7	536,2	10,83	419,8	5,05	16,8	-	-
LUSC1A	11,9	756,6	11,7	739,9	4,8	19	64	32
LUSC1B	11,9	756,6	11,7	739,9	4,8	19	64	32
LUSC2A	11,9	756,6	11,7	739,9	4,8	19	64	32
LUSC2B	11,9	756,6	11,7	739,9	4,8	19	64	32
LUSC3A	11,9	756,6	11,7	739,9	4,8	19	64	32
LUSC3B	11,9	756,6	11,7	739,9	4,8	19	64	32
LUSC4A	11,9	756,6	11,7	739,9	4,8	19	64	32

LUSC4B	11,9	756,6	11,7	739,9	4,8	19	64	32
LUSC5A	11,9	756,6	11,7	739,9	4,8	19	64	32
LUSC5B	11,9	756,6	11,7	739,9	4,8	19	64	32
LUSO1A	11,6	1493,4	12,6	1458,1	8,6	17,6	0	9
LUSO1B	11,8	1808,5	12,6	1725,3	8,1	18,1	5	13
LUSO2A	13,3	1029,9	13,7	1084,3	8,5	19,8	15	39
LUSO2B	13,3	1029,9	13,7	1084,3	8,5	19,8	15	39
LUSO3A	12,2	887	12,3	858,2	6	19,8	53	35
LUSO3B	12,1	1179,8	12,5	1230,2	7	19,1	16	29
LUSO4A	13,4	864,9	13,3	820,8	9,6	17,3	3	0
LUSO4B	13,4	864,9	13,3	820,8	9,6	17,3	3	0
LUSO4C	13,4	864,9	13,3	820,8	9,6	17,3	3	0
LUSO5A	12,1	1179,8	12,5	1230,2	7	19,1	16	29
LUSO5B	12,1	1179,8	12,5	1230,2	7	19,1	16	29
LUSO6A	11,9	756,6	11,7	739,9	4,8	19	64	32
LUSO6B	11,9	756,6	11,7	739,9	4,8	19	64	32
MNO1A	13	303	13,1/13,1	324/426	6/5,9	20,5/20,7	72/77	59/56
MNO1B	13	303	13,1/13,1	324/426	6/5,9	20,5/20,7	72/77	59/56
MNO2A	12,9	301	13,2/13,4	358/345	8,7/7,2	17,8/19,8	51/51	41/41
MNO2B	12,9	301	13,2/13,4	358/345	8,7/7,2	17,8/19,8	51/51	41/41
MNO3A	12,9	301	13,2/13,4	358/345	8,7/7,2	17,8/19,8	51/51	41/41
MNO3B	12,9	301	13,2/13,4	358/345	8,7/7,2	17,8/19,8	51/51	41/41
MNO4A	16,6	272	16,4/13,1	184/426	9,3/5,9	23,7/20,7	34/77	81/56
MNO4B	16,6	272	16,4/13,1	184/426	9,3/5,9	23,7/20,7	34/77	81/56
MNO5A	12,9	301	13,2/13,4	358/345	8,7/7,2	17,8/19,8	51/51	41/41
MNO5B	12,9	301	13,2/13,4	358/345	8,7/7,2	17,8/19,8	51/51	41/41
MNC1A	13,6	295	13,7/14,3	406/446	6,4/7,1	21,4/21,5	85/58	74/80
MNC1B	13,6	295	13,7/13,4	406/446	6,4/7,1	21,4/21,5	85/58	74/80
MNC2A	12,9	301	13,2/13,4	358/344	8,7/7,2	17,8/19,9	51/51	41/41
MNC2B	12,9	301	13,2/13,4	358/344	8,7/7,2	17,8/19,9	51/51	41/41
MNC3A	13,6	295	13,7/14,3	406/446	6,4/7,1	21,4/21,5	85/58	74/80
MNC3B	13,6	295	13,7/14,3	406/446	6,4/7,1	21,4/21,5	85/58	74/80
MNC4A	13,8	382	15,4/15	403/444	8,9/8,7	23/22,2	30/21	85/82
MNC4B	13,8	382	15,4/15	403/444	8,9/8,7	23/22,2	30/21	85/82
MNC5A	13,8	382	15,4/15	403/444	8,9/8,7	23/22,2	30/21	85/82
MNC5B	13,8	382	15,4/15	403/444	8,9/8,7	23/22,2	30/21	85/82
MSO1A	16,9	241	17/14,6	294/289	13,4/8,4	21/21,6	6/28	92/64
MSO1B	16,9	241	17/14,6	294/289	13,4/8,4	21/21,6	6/28	92/64
MSO2A	16,9	241	17/14,6	294/289	13,4/8,4	21/21,6	6/28	92/64

MSO2B	16,9	241	17/14,6	294/289	13,4/8,4	21/21,6	6/28	92/64
MSO3A	16,9	241	17/14,6	294/289	13,4/8,4	21/21,6	6/28	92/64
MSO3B	16,9	241	17/14,6	294/289	13,4/8,4	21/21,6	6/28	92/64
MSO4A	16,9	241	17/14,6	294/289	13,4/8,4	21/21,6	6/28	92/64
MSO4B	16,9	241	17/14,6	294/289	13,4/8,4	21/21,6	6/28	92/64
MSO5A	16,8	154	17,5/17,5	337/337	14,2/12,2	21,4/23	5/2	51/65
MSO5B	16,8	154	17,5/17,5	337/337	14,2/12,2	21,4/23	5/2	51/65
MSC1A	17,5	265	17,7/17,8	318/318	14,1/12,1	21,3/24,1	3/3	94/97
MSC1B	17,5	265	17,7/17,8	318/318	14,1/12,1	21,3/24,1	3/3	94/97
MSC2A	17,3	275	18,2/17,8	357/318	15/12,1	21,8/24,1	1/3	68/97
MSC2B	17,3	275	18,2/17,8	357/318	15/12,1	21,8/24,1	1/3	68/97
MSC3A	17,5	265	17,7/17,8	318/318	14,1/12,1	21,3/24,1	3/3	94/97
MSC3B	17,5	265	17,7/17,8	318/318	14,1/12,1	21,3/24,1	3/3	94/97
MSC4A	17,5	265	17,7/17,8	318/318	14,1/12,1	21,3/24,1	3/3	94/97
MSC4B	17,5	265	17,7/17,8	318/318	14,1/12,1	21,3/24,1	3/3	94/97
MSC5A	17,5	265	17,7/17,8	318/318	14,1/12,1	21,3/24,1	3/3	94/97
MSC5B	17,5	265	17,7/17,8	318/318	14,1/12,1	21,3/24,1	3/3	94/97
NEMO1A	6,3	673	8,3	727	-4,8	14,8	138	5
NEMO1B	6,3	673	8,3	727	-4,8	14,8	138	5
NEMO2A	6,3	673	8,3	727	-4,8	14,8	138	5
NEMO2B	6,3	673	8,3	727	-4,8	14,8	138	5
NEMO3A	6,2	747	8,9	822	-5,3	15,6	129	16
NEMO3B	6,2	747	8,9	822	-5,3	15,6	129	16
NEMO4A	6,8	761	8,8	763	-4	13,6	106	2
NEMO4B	6,8	761	8,8	763	-4	13,6	106	2
NEMO5A	6,8	761	8,7	763	-4,5	14,3	139	6
NEMO5B	6,8	761	8,7	763	-4,5	14,3	139	6
NEMC1A	5,4	684	7,5	732	-5,6	14,1	145	6
NEMC1B	5,4	684	7,5	732	-5,6	14,1	145	6
NEMC2A	6,2	747	8,2	822	-4,7	14,9	136	8
NEMC2B	6,2	747	8,2	822	-4,7	14,9	136	8
NEMC3A	6,8	761	7,9	857	-5	14,9	155	8
NEMC3B	6,8	761	7,9	857	-5	14,9	155	8
NEMC4A	6,3	673	8,3	727	-4,8	14,8	138	5
NEMC4B	6,3	673	8,3	727	-4,8	14,8	138	5
NEMC5A	6,3	675	8,3	750	-4,8	15,7	142	9
NEMC5B	6,3	675	8,3	750	-4,8	15,7	142	9
PANC1A	12,5	691	13,9	654,3	8,5	17,4	65	35
PANC1B	12,5	691	13,9	654,3	8,5	17,4	65	35

PANC2A	11,3	660	12,42	537	8,06	17,36	60	33
PANC2B	11,3	660	12,42	537	8,06	17,36	60	33
PANC3A	11,3	660	12,42	537	8,06	17,36	60	33
PANC3B	11,3	660	12,42	537	8,06	17,36	60	33
PANC4A	11,4	533,4	12	551,1	8,06	17,36	65	39
PANC4B	11,4	533,4	12	551,1	8,06	17,36	65	39
PANC5A	11,4	533,4	12	551,1	8,06	17,36	65	39
PANC5B	11,4	533,4	12	551,1	8,06	17,36	65	39
PANO1A	11,4	647	12,8	733,2	6,5	16,8	65	35
PANO1B	11,4	647	12,8	733,2	6,5	16,8	65	35
PANO2A	11,3	660	12,42	537	8,06	17,36	60	33
PANO2B	11,3	660	12,42	537	8,06	17,36	60	33
PANO3A	11,3	660	12,42	537	8,06	17,36	60	33
PANO3B	11,3	660	12,42	537	8,06	17,36	60	33
PANO4A	10,9	524	11,4	481,5	8,06	17,36	82	33
PANO4B	10,9	524	11,4	481,5	8,06	17,36	82	33
PANO5A	10,9	524	11,4	481,5	8,06	17,36	82	33
PANO5B	10,9	524	11,4	481,5	8,06	17,36	82	33

Table A1.2. Metadata file 2, climatological data. Mean °C 30Y = mean annual temperature (°C) of the last 30 years; Mean P 30Y = mean annual precipitation (mm) of the last 30 years; Mean °C 1Y = mean annual temperature (°C) of the last 12 months prior to the sampling event; Total P 1Y = total precipitation (mm) of the last 12 months prior to the sampling event; Mean Min. °C 1Y = average of minimum T (°C) of the last 12 months prior to the sampling event; Mean Max. °C 1Y = average of maximum T (°C) of the last 12 months prior to the sampling event; #D <0°C 1Y = number of days with T<0°C in the last 12 months prior to the sampling event; #D >30°C 1Y = number of days with T>30°C in the last 12 months prior to the sampling event. (*) In case the earthworm sampling was conducted in another period then the soil sampling, a second figure is added.

TABLE A1.3

SAMPLE ID	CROP ROTATION	LEGU-MES	IN-CORP	TILLAGE	FERTILI-ZATION	PHYTO-PRODUCTS
ACO1A	Long	Yes	No	No	Organic	None
ACO1B	Long	No	Yes	DeepInv	Organic	None
ACO1C	Long	Yes	Yes	DeepInv	Organic	H
ACO2A	Long	No	Yes	DeepInv	Organic	None
ACO3A	Long	No	Yes	DeepInv	Organic	B
ACO4A	Long	No	Yes	DeepInv	None	None
ACO4B	Short	No	Yes	DeepInv	None	None

ACO4C	Short	No	Yes	DeepInv	None	None
ACO5A	Short	Yes	No	No	None	None
ACO5B	Long	No	No	No	None	None
ACO6A	Long	Yes	No	No	Organic	None
ACO6B	Long	Yes	No	No	None	None
ACC1A	Long	Yes	No	DeepInv	Organic & mineral	H, F & I
ACC2A	Long	No	No	RedMix	Organic & mineral	H, F & I
ACC3A	Short	No	No	DeepInv	Organic & mineral	H, F & I
ACC4A	Short	No	No	DeepInv	Organic & mineral	None
ACC5A	Long	No	No	DeepInv	Mineral	H, F & I
ACC6A	Long	No	Yes	DeepInv	Organic & mineral	H, F & I
ACC6B	Long	No	Yes	DeepInv	Organic & mineral	H, F & I
ACC7A	Long	No	No	RedInv	Organic & mineral	H, F & I
ACC8A	Long	No	Yes	DeepInv	Organic & mineral	H, F & I
ACC8B	Long	No	Yes	DeepInv	Organic & mineral	H, F & I
ACC9A	Short	No	No	DeepInv	Organic & mineral	H, F & I
ACC10A	Long	No	No	DeepInv	Organic & mineral	H, F & I
ACC11A	Long	No	No	DeepInv	Organic & mineral	H, F & I
ANC1A	Short	No	Yes	DeepMix	Organic & mineral	H, F & I
ANC1B	Short	No	Yes	DeepMix	Organic & mineral	H, F & I
ANC2A	Mono	No	Yes	DeepMix	Mineral	H & F
ANC2B	Mono	No	Yes	DeepMix	Mineral	H & F
ANC3A	Short	No	Yes	DeepInv	Organic & mineral	H & F
ANC3B	Short	No	Yes	DeepInv	Organic & mineral	H & F
ANC4A	Short	No	No	DeepInv	Organic & mineral	H & F
ANC4B	Short	No	No	DeepInv	Organic & mineral	H & F
ANC5A	Short	No	No	DeepInv	Mineral	H, F & I
ANC5B	Short	No	No	DeepInv	Mineral	H, F & I
ANO1A	Short	Yes	No	DeepInv	Organic	None
ANO1B	Short	Yes	No	DeepInv	Organic	None
ANO2A	Short	No	No	DeepInv	Organic	None
ANO2B	Short	No	No	DeepInv	Organic	None
ANO3A	Short	No	Yes	DeepInv	Organic	None
ANO3B	Short	No	Yes	DeepInv	Organic	None
ANO4A	Short	Yes	No	DeepInv	Organic	None
ANO4B	Short	Yes	No	DeepInv	Organic	None
ANO5A	Short	Yes	No	DeepInv	Organic	None
ANO5B	Short	No	No	DeepInv	Organic	None
BORO1A	Short	Yes	Yes	DeepInv	Organic	None

BORO1B	Short	Yes	Yes	DeepInv	Organic	None
BORC1A	Short	No	No	DeepMix	Mineral	H & F
BORC1B	Short	Yes	No	DeepMix	Mineral	H & F
BORO2A	Short	Yes	No	DeepInv	Organic	None
BORO2B	Short	Yes	No	DeepInv	Organic	None
BORC2A	Short	No	Yes	DeepInv	Mineral	H
BORC2B	Short	No	Yes	DeepInv	Mineral	H
BORO3A	Long	Yes	No	DeepInv	Organic	None
BORO3B	Long	Yes	No	DeepInv	Organic	None
BORC3A	Short	No	No	No	Organic & mineral	H
BORC3B	Short	No	No	No	Organic & mineral	H
BORO4A	Short	Yes	No	DeepInv	Organic	None
BORO4B	Short	Yes	No	DeepInv	Organic	None
BORC4A	Short	No	No	DeepInv	Organic & mineral	H
BORC4B	Long	Yes	Yes	DeepInv	Organic & mineral	H
BORO5A	Long	Yes	Yes	DeepInv	Organic	None
BORO5B	Long	Yes	Yes	DeepInv	Organic	None
BORC5A	Short	Yes	Yes	DeepMix	Mineral	H
BORC5B	Short	Yes	Yes	DeepMix	Mineral	H
CONC1A	Short	No	No	DeepMix	Organic	H & F
CONC1B	Short	No	No	DeepMix	Organic	H & F
CONC1C	Short	No	No	DeepMix	Organic	H & F
CONC2A	Short	No	No	DeepMix	Organic & mineral	H & F
CONC2B	Short	No	No	DeepMix	Organic & mineral	H & F
CONC2C	Short	No	No	DeepMix	Organic & mineral	H & F
CONC3A	Short	No	No	DeepMix	Mineral	H, F & I
CONC3B	Short	No	No	DeepMix	Mineral	H, F & I
CONC3C	Short	No	No	DeepMix	Mineral	H, F & I
CONC4A	Short	No	No	No	Organic & mineral	H, F & I
CONO1A	Long	No	No	DeepInv	None	None
CONO1B	Long	No	No	DeepInv	None	None
CONO1C	Long	Yes	No	DeepInv	Organic	None
CONO2A	Long	Yes	No	DeepInv	None	None
CONO2B	Long	Yes	No	DeepInv	None	None
CONO2C	Long	Yes	No	DeepInv	None	None
CONO3A	Long	Yes	No	DeepInv	Organic	None
CONO4A	Long	Yes	No	DeepInv	Organic	None
CONO4B	Long	No	No	DeepInv	Organic	None
CONO4C	Long	No	No	DeepInv	Organic	None

LUSC1A	Short	No	No	DeepInv	Organic	H
LUSC1B	Short	No	No	DeepInv	Organic	H
LUSC2A	Short	No	No	DeepInv	Mineral	H, F & I
LUSC2B	Mono	No	No	DeepInv	Organic	H, F & I
LUSC3A	Short	No	No	DeepInv	Organic	H, F & I
LUSC3B	Short	No	No	DeepInv	Organic	H, F & I
LUSC4A	Short	No	No	DeepInv	Mineral	H, F & I
LUSC4B	Short	No	No	DeepInv	Mineral	H, F & I
LUSC5A	Mono	No	No	DeepMix	Mineral	H
LUSC5B	Mono	No	No	DeepMix	Mineral	H & I
LUSO1A	Short	No	Yes	DeepMix	Organic	None
LUSO1B	Short	No	No	DeepInv	None	None
LUSO2A	Mono	No	No	DeepMix	None	None
LUSO2B	Short	No	No	DeepMix	None	None
LUSO3A	Short	No	No	DeepInv	Organic	None
LUSO3B	Short	Yes	No	DeepInv	Organic	None
LUSO4A	Short	No	No	DeepInv	None	None
LUSO4B	Short	No	No	DeepInv	None	None
LUSO4C	Short	No	No	DeepInv	None	None
LUSO5A	Short	No	No	DeepInv	Organic	None
LUSO5B	Short	No	No	DeepInv	Organic	None
LUSO6A	Mono	No	No	DeepMix	Organic	None
LUSO6B	Mono	No	No	DeepMix	Organic	None
MNO1A	Short	No	No	DeepInv	Organic	None
MNO1B	Short	No	No	DeepInv	Organic	None
MNO2A	Short	No	No	DeepInv	Organic	None
MNO2B	Short	No	No	DeepInv	Organic	None
MNO3A	Short	No	No	DeepInv	Organic	None
MNO3B	Short	No	No	DeepInv	Organic	None
MNO4A	Short	No	No	DeepInv	Organic	None
MNO4B	Short	No	No	DeepInv	Organic	None
MNO5A	Short	No	No	DeepInv	None	None
MNO5B	Short	No	No	DeepInv	None	None
MNC1A	Short	No	No	DeepInv	None	None
MNC1B	Short	No	No	DeepInv	None	None
MNC2A	Mono	No	No	DeepInv	Mineral	H
MNC2B	Mono	No	No	DeepInv	Mineral	H
MNC3A	Short	No	No	DeepInv	Organic	None
MNC3B	Short	No	No	DeepInv	Organic	None

MNC4A	Short	No	No	DeepInv	Mineral	H
MNC4B	Short	No	No	DeepInv	Mineral	H
MNC5A	Short	No	No	DeepInv	Organic	H
MNC5B	Short	No	No	DeepInv	Organic	H
MSO1A	Short	Yes	No	DeepInv	None	None
MSO1B	Short	Yes	No	DeepInv	None	None
MSO2A	Short	No	No	DeepInv	None	None
MSO2B	Short	No	No	DeepInv	None	None
MSO3A	Short	No	No	DeepInv	None	None
MSO3B	Short	No	No	DeepInv	None	None
MSO4A	Short	No	No	DeepInv	Organic	None
MSO4B	Short	No	No	DeepInv	Organic	None
MSO5A	Mono	No	No	DeepInv	None	None
MSO5B	Mono	No	No	DeepInv	None	None
MSC1A	Mono	No	No	DeepInv	None	None
MSC1B	Mono	No	No	DeepInv	None	None
MSC2A	Mono	No	No	DeepInv	None	None
MSC2B	Mono	No	No	DeepInv	None	None
MSC3A	Short	Yes	No	DeepInv	Organic	F, H, I & B
MSC3B	Short	Yes	No	DeepInv	Organic	F, H, I & B
MSC4A	Short	Yes	No	DeepInv	Organic	F, H, I & B
MSC4B	Short	Yes	No	DeepInv	Organic	F, H, I & B
MSC5A	Short	Yes	No	DeepInv	Organic	F, H, I & B
MSC5B	Short	Yes	No	DeepInv	Organic	F, H, I & B
NEMO1A	Long	Yes	No	DeepInv	None	None
NEMO1B	Long	Yes	No	DeepInv	None	None
NEMO2A	Long	Yes	Yes	DeepInv	None	None
NEMO2B	Long	Yes	Yes	DeepInv	None	None
NEMO3A	Long	Yes	Yes	DeepInv	Organic	None
NEMO3B	Long	Yes	Yes	DeepInv	Organic	None
NEMO4A	Long	Yes	No	DeepInv	Organic	None
NEMO4B	Long	Yes	No	DeepInv	Organic	None
NEMO5A	Long	Yes	No	DeepInv	Organic	None
NEMO5B	Long	Yes	No	DeepInv	Organic	None
NEMC1A	Long	No	No	RedInv	Mineral	H, F & I
NEMC1B	Long	No	No	RedInv	Mineral	H, F & I
NEMC2A	Long	No	No	RedMix	Mineral	H, F & I
NEMC2B	Long	No	No	RedMix	Mineral	H, F & I
NEMC3A	Long	Yes	No	No	Mineral	H, F & I

NEMC3B	Long	Yes	No	No	Mineral	H, F & I
NEMC4A	Long	No	No	No	Mineral	H, F & I
NEMC4B	Long	No	No	No	Mineral	H, F & I
NEMC5A	Short	Yes	No	DeepInv	Organic & mineral	H
NEMC5B	Short	Yes	No	DeepInv	Organic & mineral	H
PANC1A	Short	No	No	DeepInv	Mineral	H & I
PANC1B	Short	No	No	DeepInv	Mineral	H & I
PANC2A	Short	No	No	DeepInv	Mineral	H & F
PANC2B	Short	No	No	DeepInv	Mineral	H & F
PANC3A	Short	No	No	DeepInv	None	F & I
PANC3B	Short	No	No	DeepInv	None	F & I
PANC4A	Short	No	No	DeepInv	Organic & mineral	H, F & I
PANC4B	Short	No	No	DeepInv	Organic & mineral	H, F & I
PANC5A	Short	No	No	DeepInv	Organic & mineral	H, F & I
PANC5B	Short	No	No	DeepInv	Organic & mineral	H, F & I
PANO1A	Long	Yes	Yes	DeepInv	Organic	None
PANO1B	Long	Yes	Yes	DeepInv	Organic	None
PANO2A	Mono	No	No	No	None	None
PANO2B	Short	No	Yes	DeepInv	None	None
PANO3A	Short	Yes	Yes	DeepInv	Organic	None
PANO3B	Short	No	Yes	DeepInv	Organic	None
PANO4A	Short	No	No	DeepMix	Organic	B
PANO4B	Short	No	No	DeepMix	Organic	B
PANO5A	Short	Yes	No	DeepMix	Organic	B
PANO5B	Short	Yes	No	DeepMix	Organic	B

Table A1.3. Metadata file 3, management practices. CROP ROTATION: mono = wheat monoculture with fallow, short = short rotation with 2 to 3 different crops, long = long rotation with more than 3 different crops; LEGUMES = crop rotation with legumes or not; INCORP = crop residues were incorporated or not; TILLAGE: DeepInv = conventional tillage - deep soil inversion (ploughing till a depth of 15-35 cm, typically 25 cm), RedInv = conventional tillage - shallow soil inversion (shallow ploughing/disc harrowing till a depth of 10-12 cm, No = no mixing or inversion of the soil (direct seeding, subsoiler), DeepMix = reduced tillage - deep soil mixing without inversion (cultivator, spader, rotavader till a depth of 15-35 cm, typically 25 cm), RedMix = reduced tillage – shallow soil mixing without inversion (harrow other than disc harrow till a depth of 10-12 cm); PHYTOPRODUCTS: H = Herbicides, F = Fungicides, I = Insecticides, B = biocides.

TABLE A4.1

REGION	CRS	EI-MEAN	EI-SD	P	SI-MEAN	SI-SD	P
Atl_cent	Long	64.84	17.93	0.826	54.19	24.79	0.191

	Short	66.59	10.73		39.82	12.68	
Atl_north	Mono	32.25	7.20	0.154	32.27	25.61	0.108
	Short	51.29	17.59		61.54	23.11	
Boreal	Long	59.63	35.22	0.928	76.21	13.33	0.413
	Short	58.36	23.69		68.58	18.65	
Cont	Long	67.06	16.73	0.555	38.41	31.71	0.626
	Short	62.92	13.18		31.61	27.97	
Lusit	Mono	70.91	12.97	0.318	20.72	30.31	0.100
	Short	59.86	24.54		50.67	36.58	
Med_north	Mono	37.03	3.89	0.634	62.77	6.20	0.231
	Short	32.13	13.97		44.73	20.05	
Med_south	Mono	33.08	5.01	0.820	31.44	10.20	0.663
	Short	35.52	20.55		37.07	24.33	
Nemoral	Long	52.52	13.82	0.867	59.43	11.29	0.588
	Short	54.24	7.54		54.90	5.00	
Pann	Long	47.36	9.39	0.135	41.63	12.78	0.225
	Mono	41.87	NA		34.15	NA	
	Short	55.62	7.69		21.52	16.00	

Table A4.1. Mean and standard deviation (SD) values of the nematode specific Enrichment (EI) and Structure Index (SI) linked to the different crop rotation systems (CRS) used in each region. Atl_cent = Atlantic Central, Atl_north = Atlantic North, Boreal = Boreal, Cont = Continental, Lusit = Lusitanian, Med_north = Mediterranean North, Med_south = Mediterranean South, Nemoral = Nemoral, Pann = Pannonian; CRS: mono = wheat monoculture with fallow, short = short rotation with 2 to 3 different crops, long = long rotation with more than 3 different crops.

TABLE A4.2

REGION	TILLAGE	EI-MEAN	EI-SD	P	SI-MEAN	SI-SD	P
Atl_cent	DeepInv	64.63	16.91	0.781	51.44	22.69	0.184
	No	65.53	17.07		37.46	18.56	
	RedInv	58.90	NA		89.89	NA	
	RedMix	81.52	NA		62.62	NA	
Atl_north	DeepInv	54.18	16.21	0.011	64.56	22.36	0.024
	DeepMix	30.19	7.83		34.83	17.78	
Boreal	DeepInv	61.21	26.99	0.818	75.19	18.61	0.181
	DeepMix	52.56	22.48		58.03	8.72	
	No	53.18	39.25		62.49	3.09	
Cont	DeepInv	67.06	16.73	0.080	38.41	31.71	0.066
	DeepMix	59.64	8.62		24.80	18.92	

	No	92.46	NA		92.94	NA	
Lusit	DeepInv	60.43	24.72	0.406	46.83	35.57	0.342
	DeepMix	69.68	13.31		29.05	39.62	
Med_north	DeepInv	32.62	13.33	NA	46.54	19.81	NA
Med_south	DeepInv	34.97	18.12	NA	35.82	21.83	NA
Nemoral	DeepInv	56.15	7.54	0.048	56.71	9.30	0.493
	No	53.00	19.50		61.50	15.12	
	RedInv	29.14	15.71		69.22	9.67	
	RedMix	54.91	5.47		57.37	13.92	
Pann	DeepInv	54.54	9.09	0.341	25.18	18.06	0.674
	DeepMix	55.29	2.62		18.73	10.86	
	No	41.87	NA		34.15	NA	

Table A4.2. Mean and standard deviation (SD) values of the nematode specific Enrichment (EI) and Structure Index (SI) linked to the different tillage methods used in each region. Atl_cent = Atlantic Central, Atl_north = Atlantic North, Boreal = Boreal, Cont = Continental, Lusit = Lusitanian, Med_north = Mediterranean North, Med_south = Mediterranean South, Nemoral = Nemoral, Pann = Pannonian; TILLAGE: DeepInv = conventional tillage - deep soil inversion (ploughing till a depth of 15-35 cm, typically 25 cm), RedInv = conventional tillage - shallow soil inversion (shallow ploughing/disc harrowing till a depth of 10-12 cm, No = no mixing or inversion of the soil (direct seeding, subsoiler), DeepMix = reduced tillage - deep soil mixing without inversion (cultivator, spader, rotavader till a depth of 15-35 cm, typically 25 cm), RedMix = reduced tillage – shallow soil mixing without inversion (harrow other than disc harrow till a depth of 10-12 cm).

TABLE A4.3

REGION	FERTILI-ZATION	EI-MEAN	EI-SD	P	SI-MEAN	SI-SD	P
Atl_cent	Mineral	64.34	NA	0.476	44.03	NA	0.848
	None	56.08	18.16		48.99	25.92	
	Organic	68.80	21.74		44.07	29.98	
	Organic & mineral	68.49	12.86		54.66	20.79	
Atl_north	Mineral	33.08	4.29	0.001	38.29	18.89	0.001
	Organic	62.28	14.95		76.44	14.88	
	Organic & mineral	38.76	9.95		42.46	19.05	
Boreal	Mineral	58.95	25.34	0.993	66.42	15.63	0.272
	Organic	59.09	29.44		76.65	11.77	
	Organic & mineral	57.23	24.55		61.20	28.90	
Cont	Mineral	67.00	1.69	0.986	13.23	4.60	0.591
	None	64.45	23.68		37.26	39.74	
	Organic	63.59	12.86		41.46	24.03	

	Organic & mineral	66.33	18.28		35.35	39.61	
Lusit	Mineral	60.37	26.67	0.807	12.50	17.01	0.030
	None	71.03	6.44		79.75	2.48	
	Organic	62.61	23.27		43.76	38.10	
Med_north	Mineral	29.28	9.54	0.619	40.53	27.54	0.717
	None	28.52	6.20		52.49	15.39	
	Organic	35.10	15.96		46.55	19.50	
Med_south	None	37.62	20.19	0.505	37.53	20.60	0.723
	Organic	31.66	15.83		33.69	24.56	
	Mineral	47.51	18.22	0.449	62.39	12.65	0.659
Nemoral	None	60.85	9.59		59.61	3.48	
	Organic	53.66	5.66		55.37	12.96	
	Organic & mineral	54.24	7.54		54.90	5.00	
Pann	Mineral	56.21	5.77	0.695	31.06	27.01	0.788
	None	49.59	10.08		24.51	13.80	
	Organic	54.26	7.09		23.57	16.04	
	Organic & mineral	55.87	12.04		18.59	8.30	

Table A4.3. Mean and standard deviation (SD) values of the nematode specific Enrichment (EI) and Structure Index (SI) linked to the different fertilization methods used in each region. Atl_cent = Atlantic Central, Atl_north = Atlantic North, Boreal = Boreal, Cont = Continental, Lusit = Lusitanian, Med_north = Mediterranean North, Med_south = Mediterranean South, Nemoral = Nemoral, Pann = Pannonian; mono = wheat monoculture with fallow, short = short rotation with 2 to 3 different crops, long = long rotation with more than 3 different crops.

TABLE A4.4

REGION	PHYTO-PRODUCTS	EI-MEAN	EI-SD	P	SI-MEAN	SI-SD	P
Atl_cent	Bio	34.69	NA	0.147	84.88	NA	0.169
	H, F & I	67.76	12.82		54.26	20.95	
	None	65.36	17.99		43.48	23.36	
Atl_north	H & F	40.13	7.48	0.001	40.75	21.65	0.001
	H, F & I	31.02	7.05		40.85	13.94	
	None	62.28	14.95		76.44	14.88	
Boreal	H & F	67.22	24.90	0.873	63.04	10.95	0.301
	H	56.02	24.51		64.65	22.89	
	None	59.09	29.44		76.65	11.77	
Cont	H & F	55.96	8.30	0.155	30.58	21.06	0.884
	H, F & I	73.37	12.81		33.16	40.03	

	None	67.06	16.73		38.41	31.71	
Lusit	H, F & I	58.51	22.19	0.686	34.14	28.48	0.025
	H & I	86.10	NA		1.12	NA	
	H	58.34	32.58		1.78	2.06	
	None	65.72	20.01		63.53	33.94	
Med_north	H	27.05	8.44	0.230	44.75	23.31	0.800
	None	35.01	14.55		47.30	19.04	
Med_south	H, F & I	30.34	15.02	0.460	22.47	15.47	0.064
	None	37.29	19.68		42.50	21.96	
Nemoral	H, F & I	47.51	18.22	0.368	62.39	12.65	0.524
	H	54.24	7.54		54.90	5.00	
	None	56.53	7.89		57.07	10.11	
Pann	Bio	55.29	2.62	0.836	18.73	10.86	0.491
	F & I	46.24	3.80		12.98	5.66	
	H & F	55.34	9.14		23.14	27.65	
	H, F & I	55.87	12.04		18.59	8.30	
	H & I	57.08	3.64		38.99	34.24	
	None	52.92	11.37		32.43	15.99	

Table A4.4. Mean and standard deviation (SD) values of the nematode specific Enrichment (EI) and Structure Index (SI) linked to the application of phytoproducts in each region. Atl_cent = Atlantic Central, Atl_north = Atlantic North, Boreal = Boreal, Cont = Continental, Lusit = Lusitanian, Med_north = Mediterranean North, Med_south = Mediterranean South, Nemoral = Nemoral, Pann = Pannonian; PHYTOPRODUCTS: H = Herbicides, F = Fungicides, I = Insecticides, B = biocides.

ANNEXES-figures

Figure A1.1. Relative abundance (%) of top 20 genera which were differentially abundant between different crop rotation systems as determined by differential abundance analysis (ANCOMBC). The rotation systems included wheat monoculture with fallow years (Mono), short rotation with 2-3 different crops (Short), or long rotation with >4 different crops (Long).

Figure A1.2. Relative abundance (%) of genera which were differentially abundant between systems using different fertilization regimes as determined by differential abundance analysis (ANCOMBC). The fertilization regimes included no fertilizers (none), organic fertilizer (Organic), mineral fertilizer (Mineral), or a mix between organic and mineral fertilizer (Organic & mineral).

Figure A1.3. Relative abundance (%) of top 20 genera which were differentially abundant between systems using different types of pesticide as determined by differential abundance analysis (ANCOMBC). The pesticide types included no pesticides (None), herbicides (H), biocides (B), herbicide and fungicide (H & F), herbicide, fungicide and insecticide (H, F & I), or fungicide, herbicide, insecticide and biocide (F, H, I & B).

Figure A1.4. Relative abundance (%) of genera which were differentially abundant between systems incorporating residual crops remnants into the soil (Yes) and systems that do not incorporate residual crops (No) as determined by differential abundance analysis (ANCOMBC).

Figure A1.5. Relative abundance (%) of genera which were differentially abundant between systems including legumes in crop rotation (Yes) and systems not including legumes (No) as determined by differential abundance analysis (ANCOMBC).

Figure A1.6. Relative abundance (%) of top 20 genera which were differentially abundant between different tillage systems as determined by differential abundance analysis (ANCOMBC). Tillage systems included; No = no mixing or inversion of the soil (direct seeding, subsoiler), DeepInv = conventional tillage - deep soil inversion (ploughing till a depth of 15-35 cm, typically 25 cm), DeepMix = reduced tillage - deep soil mixing without inversion (cultivator, spader, rotavader till a depth of 15-35 cm, typically 25 cm), or Red = either shallow soil inversion (shallow ploughing/disc harrowing till a depth of 10-12 cm or shallow soil mixing without inversion (harrow other than disc harrow till a depth of 10-12 cm).